

FACULTY'S RESPONSIVE TEACHING STRATEGIES AND STUDENTS' CULTURAL COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE IN MARINDUQUE STATE COLLEGE: BASIS FOR SDG ALIGNED CURRICULUM FRAMEWORK

Ma. Jessica L. Semilla, Leodegario M. Jalos, Jr.

Graduate School, Marinduque State University, Marinduque, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14253298>

ABSTRACT

This study aimed to develop a proposed curriculum framework aligned with Sustainable Development Goals through cultural communicative competence and utilization of responsive teaching strategies among faculty members at selected colleges in Marinduque State College (MSC). A mixed-method design was employed, using both quantitative and qualitative approaches. A purposive sampling was utilized to select ten faculty members handling Purposive Communication subject and eight hundred fifty-five students enrolled (with)in this subject, Second Semester A.Y. 2023-2024 in MSC. Data collection involved a competence test, classroom observation tool, and Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) to assess teaching strategies and cultural competence. Findings reveal high utilization of responsive teaching strategies across various domains by MSC faculty, with no significant differences observed among colleges. However, there were significant differences in cultural communicative competence levels among MSC students across colleges. Identified themes through FGDs include fostering a positive learning environment, diverse student learning styles, online modalities, language barriers, and teacher flexibility. Based on these findings, a curriculum framework emphasizing cultural communicative competency for the Purposive Communication course at MSC is proposed. This framework is aligned to the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal to promote more contextualized learning and cultural sensitivity among students. The study emphasizes prioritizing cultural competency in teaching practices and suggests personalized strategies to enhance students' cultural communicative competence.

Keywords: *Curriculum Framework, Cultural Communicative Competence, Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), Responsive Teaching Strategies, Purposive Communication*

INTRODUCTION

Changes in the educational framework are a new dimension of the twenty-first century, hence calling one to think about the ways education can be of service to change the needs of students and society. The United Nations through SDGs, quality education as SDG 4 and reduced inequalities as SDG 10 have an all-inclusive approach to transform the education structure that could be inclusive, equal, and flexible in meeting the needs of modern society. SDG 4 It is, basically, based on high-quality education that promotes critical thinking, creativity, communication, and cooperation-an essential competence to thrive in the 21st century (Driscoll, n.d.). SDG 10 addresses the issue of inequalities through the provision of equal access to education for disadvantaged groups to be achieved, as well as enhancing cultural acceptance and social integration in an environment that offers education (Alda & Boholano, 2020). Thus, education systems must be designed in ways that ensure that all learners, especially those from underrepresented backgrounds, are provided with skills relevant to a more globalized world (Alda & Boholano, 2020; TESDA, 2021). The above goals call for education policies that will enhance the capabilities of students for the changing workforce as stepped progressions toward social justice and fairness.

As such, intercultural communicative competence has emerged to play an important role in the modern education context, since it has been found to help students communicate effectively across cultural lines, thereby promoting mutual understanding and cooperation in diverse global milieus (Kapur, 2018). The 4th Industrial Revolution (4IR) and Education 4.0 further underscore the integration of technology in education to improve learning experience and cultural competencies (Alda & Boholano, 2020). Education 4.0 focuses on offering digital technology tailored to students' needs while engaging them in active participation as well as developing cultural communicative competencies (Alda & Boholano, 2020). Futures Thinking is another critical strategy that makes educational curricula align with long-term goals and ensures that there is development of forward-thinking attitudes, adaptability, and innovation (TESDA, 2021). In this regard, culturally responsive teaching becomes inevitable as it ensures students embrace diversity regardless of where they come from. CRT fosters inclusivity by incorporating students' cultural strengths and creating learning environments that promote equitable academic outcomes for all learners (Gay, 2018; Sabornie & Espelage, 2022). By emphasizing flexible teaching methods and community engagement, CRT aligns with SDG 10, helping to reduce educational disparities and promote a more just society (Smith & Reyes, 2019; Rodriguez, 2019).

Despite these advances, the ICC and culturally responsive teaching remain a significant practice to be integrated into education: many teachers face challenges in teaching how to help learners achieve cultural competence: far too many focus on mere aspects of

culture rather than the more contextualized understanding (Byram 1997; Sercu 2005). The researchers of this study have found a gap within the effective usage of responsive teaching strategies and the development of ICC within the students, most specifically under the higher education system of the Philippines. These aforementioned barriers are big class size, fewer resources, as well as an insufficient amount of professional development opportunities for the educators (Santos & Cruz, 2018). The inclusion of ICC in the language class, researchers conclude, would bridge the cultural gap and reduce disparities in learners' achievements for studies done in countries such as the U.S., UK, and Southeast Asia (Garcia, 2022; Deardorff, 2006; Fantini & Tirmizi, 2006). For instance, in the Philippines, the government restructured the educational system in response to the ASEAN Economic Community and Education for All goals, with a specific emphasis on improving English Language Education (ELE) (Bautista et al., 2009). Challenges still remain, though, in being able to properly address diverse student needs. This study aimed to determine the level of utilization of responsive teaching strategies by faculty members in Marinduque State College and the corresponding cultural communicative competence of students enrolled in Purposive Communication courses. The research study determined and analyzed these variables in order to provide a curriculum framework, fitting the charter of SDGs 4 and 10, in order to adjust the existing curriculum, thereby mitigating inequality and promoting a diverse and multicultural setting for education.

Research Questions

This study aimed to assess the level of utilization of responsive teaching strategies by Purposive Communication faculty at Marinduque State College, as well as the level of cultural communicative competence of their students. The findings serve as a basis for the development of a curriculum framework aligned with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly SDG 4 (Quality Education) and SDG 10 (Reduced Inequalities).

Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the level of utilization of responsive teaching strategies among Marinduque State College faculty in terms of:
 - 1.1 Curriculum Design;
 - 1.2 Classroom Relationships;
 - 1.3 Instructional Practices;
 - 1.4 Discourse; and
 - 1.5 Assessment Practices?
2. Is there a significant difference in the level of utilization of responsive teaching strategies of Marinduque State College Purposive Communication faculty when grouped?
 - 2.1 By college; and
 - 2.2 By domain
3. What is the level of cultural communicative competence of Marinduque State College students in terms of:
 - 3.1 Cultural Knowledge; and

3.2 Cultural Skills?

4. Is there a significant difference in the level of cultural communicative competence of Marinduque State College students when grouped?
 - 4.1 By college; and
 - 4.2 By domain
5. Is there a significant relationship between the level of utilization of responsive teaching strategies of Marinduque State College Purposive Communication faculty and the level of cultural communicative competence of Marinduque State College students?
6. What are the challenges encountered by Marinduque State College faculty in the utilization of responsive teaching strategies, and what interventions have been implemented to address these challenges?
7. Based on the results of the study, what curriculum framework aligned with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals could be proposed to enhance the current curriculum at Marinduque State College?

The study explored these questions to identify areas of improvement in teaching strategies and student competencies, providing actionable insights for the development of a more inclusive and effective curriculum.

METHODOLOGY

This study sought to determine the levels of utilization of Purposive Communication faculty members on responsive teaching strategies and the level of cultural communicative competence among students of Marinduque State College during the second semester of Academic Year 2023-2024. The research is basically on knowing the appropriation of the faculty members on responsive teaching strategies by evaluating them through direct observation in the classrooms, peer assessment, and self-assessment. These observations were analyzed based on some of the critical components of teaching, such as classroom relationships, forms of assessment, instructional strategies, discourse, and curriculum design by language experts. Besides, the students' cultural competence, in terms of knowledge and skills, was also discussed, ranging from adaptability, challenging discriminatory behavior, understanding the personal family history, to recognition of cultural limitations. For the assessment of these competencies, cultural competence tests and cultural logs were used to measure students' cognitive levels and performance tasks. Findings from faculty and student data were triangulated with more observations and focus group discussions to get an overall interpretation of the results. This study also pursued the relationship between responsive teaching strategies and cultural communicative competency by identifying faculty challenges and interventions in their application.

The scope of the study only focused on assessing faculty and student experiences within the context of the Purposive Communication courses of Marinduque State College. It did not include other elements or components of the intercultural communicative

competence, such as those related to attitudes in culture or awareness. Neither was it aimed at assessing other influences possibly involved, including socio-economic background or students' previous experience with multicultural environments. A purposive sampling was utilized to identify faculty members and students from four colleges offering Purposive Communication courses, amounting to 10 faculty members and 855 students. This research instrument was designed as a revision of studies from Garcia (2002), Fantini (2000), Spencer-Oatey & Franklin (2009), and Brown et al. (2021). It was content validated by seven language specialists, curriculum developers, and cultural education experts. The test thus was found valid with a high mean score ranging from 3.6 to 4.0. To ascertain the reliability of the instrument, there was a pilot test at Marinduque Midwest College. Data gathering involved classroom observations, cultural competence tests, cultural logs, and interviews. Analysis was done using both descriptive statistics, the Kruskal-Wallis tests, and Spearman's rho. The qualitative data from the FGDs were analyzed through a thematic analysis of common themes emerging around faculty challenges and interventions. A mixed-methods research design with an Explanatory Sequential Design was applied in this study, using both quantitative and qualitative approaches together to analyze the linkage between teaching strategies and cultural competence in line with sustaining the effort for developing a culturally responsive curriculum aligned with sustainable development goals.

RESULTS

I. Level of Utilization of Responsive Teaching Strategies Among the Marinduque State College Faculty

Table 1.1

Level of Utilization of Responsive Teaching Strategies Among the Marinduque State College Faculty in terms of Curriculum Design

Indicators	Level of Utilization				Grand Mean	VI
	C1	C2	C3	C4		
1. The teacher employs a curriculum and carefully designs learning experiences that offer chances to incorporate significant issues pertaining to the classroom, school, and community.	4.16	3.89	4.33	3.56	4.08	HU
2. The teacher employs a curriculum and carefully designs learning experiences that include chances to address and challenge negative stereotypes and biases.	4.09	3.69	4.17	4.11	4.03	HU
3. The teacher utilizes the curriculum and carefully designs learning experiences to incorporate and facilitate the expression of various viewpoints.	3.98	4.06	4.17	3.78	4.01	HU
4. The teacher incorporates a curriculum that explicitly covers the definition, nature, and components of intercultural communication as key subjects within the course.	4.24	3.81	4.06	4.11	4.11	HU
5. The teacher incorporates a curriculum that explicitly focuses on language varieties and cultural diversity as the	4.02	3.89	4.00	4.11	4.00	HU

main subject matter in the course through contextual activities reflected in the syllabus like essays, projects, presentations, or portfolios.

6. The teacher implements a curriculum that incorporates specific learning outcomes and objectives pertaining to intercultural and global learning. These are clearly outlined in the course syllabus or weekly plan.	4.13	4.06	4.39	4.11	4.17	HU
7. The teacher utilizes a curriculum that prioritizes the cultivation of students' intercultural awareness and sensitivity, with the aim of fostering their proficiency as effective communicators.	3.97	3.92	4.11	4.22	4.01	HU
8. The teacher incorporates a curriculum that includes intercultural and cultural topics that are directly related to communication, as evidenced in the syllabus.	4.07	4.03	4.17	4.11	4.08	HU
9. The teacher employs a curriculum that includes a variety of instructional activities, with the goal of fostering students' communication skills in multicultural and multilingual environments.	3.79	3.78	4.33	4.11	3.93	HU
10. The teacher utilizes a curriculum that incorporates specific learning outcomes and objectives pertaining to intercultural and global learning. These are explicitly outlined in the course syllabus or weekly plan.	4.20	4.22	4.17	4.22	4.20	HU

	Composite Mean	4.07	3.94	4.19	4.04	4.06	HU
Legend:	Mean Interval	Verbal Interpretation (VI)					
	4.21 - 5.00	Very Highly Utilized (VHU)		C1 - College 1			
	3.41 - 4.20	Highly Utilized (HU)		C2 - College 2			
	2.61-3.40	Moderately Utilized (MU)		C3 - College 3			
	1.81-2.60	Less Utilized (LU)		C4 - College 4			
	1.00 - 1.81	Not Utilized (NU)					

Table 1.2

Level of Utilization of Responsive Teaching Strategies Among the Marinduque State College Faculty in terms of Classroom Relationships

Indicators	Level of Utilization				Total Mean	VI
	College 1	College 2	College 3	College 4		
1. The teacher exemplifies an ethos of compassion, characterized by fair and inclusive relationships and a sense of connection.	4.07	4.00	4.11	4.22	4.08	HU
2. The teacher conveys elevated expectations for every student.	3.69	3.64	4.28	3.78	3.81	HU
3. The teacher fosters an educational environment that cultivates mutual respect among students and promotes inclusivity towards diverse communities. Students are encouraged to listen actively and respond respectfully during discussions.	3.93	3.89	4.33	4.22	4.03	HU
4. The teacher fosters productive collaboration among the students.	3.97	3.89	3.95	4.00	3.95	HU

Composite Mean		3.92	3.86	4.17	4.06	3.97	HU
Legend:	Mean Interval	Verbal Interpretation (VI)					
	4.21 - 5.00	Very Highly Utilized (VHU)					
	3.41 - 4.20	Highly Utilized (HU)					
	2.61-3.40	Moderately Utilized (MU)					
	1.81-2.60	Less Utilized (LU)					
	1.00 - 1.81	Not Utilized (NU)					

Table 1.3

Level of Utilization of Responsive Teaching Strategies Among the Marinduque State College Faculty in terms of Instructional Practices

Indicators	Level of Utilization					VI
	C1	C2	C3	C4	Total Mean	
1. The teacher employs contextualized instruction that is customized based on students' backgrounds and unique aptitudes.	4.04	3.78	4.17	4.00	4.01	HU
2. The teacher promotes active, experiential, and purposeful learning activities, which involve inquiry-based learning.	3.78	4.00	4.11	4.00	3.91	HU
3. The teacher prioritizes the development of students' academic language skills.	3.74	3.89	4.22	4.11	3.91	HU
4. The teacher employs instructional strategies that provide a supportive framework for facilitating student learning.	3.72	3.72	4.28	3.67	3.83	HU
5. The teacher offers students a range of options tailored to their individual experiences, interests, and strengths.	3.91	4.00	4.00	3.89	3.94	HU
6. The teacher utilizes audio-visual materials, such as films, slides, and podcasts, to introduce linguistic and cultural diversity in the context of communication.	3.96	3.89	4.39	4.00	4.03	HU
7. The teacher utilizes information and communication technology (ICT) resources, such as social media sites and web browsers, to involve students in diverse cultural and communicative experiences, thereby enhancing the teaching process.	3.88	4.06	4.28	4.00	4.01	HU
8. The teacher utilizes printed resources and academic readings to foster a critical understanding of diverse cultural perspectives and paradigms as instructional materials.	3.72	3.83	4.45	3.67	3.88	HU
9. The teacher incorporates the significance and impact of cultural diversity in communication as a prominent theme in the course.	3.97	3.61	4.28	4.00	3.96	HU
10. The teacher includes lessons on the management of intercultural communication, both oral and written, in various settings such as the workplace, social gatherings, and academic environments. This topic is clearly emphasized throughout the course.	3.81	3.72	4.22	4.00	3.89	HU
11. The teacher employs oral communication exercises that involve students interacting with speakers from diverse cultural backgrounds and native languages through students' presentations, roleplays, projects, and cultural interaction logs.	3.58	3.67	4.00	4.11	3.73	HU
12. The teacher ensures that students are motivated to engage in written communication with individuals from diverse linguistic and cultural backgrounds to refine their formal communication abilities like students' written communications, such as emails, letters, or essays, demonstrating engagement with diverse individuals.	3.68	3.89	3.95	3.78	3.78	HU
13. The teacher assigns students tasks to contemplate their reactions to cultural and linguistic diversity in communication.	3.88	4.22	4.00	4.00	3.98	HU
14. The teacher makes use of activities for perspective taking in managing communication are incorporated in the classroom activities	3.68	3.61	3.83	3.56	3.68	HU

15. The teacher provides preliminary activities to students to prepare them to accept and understand their role in the communication process.	3.81	3.83	4.33	4.11	3.95	HU
16. The teacher makes use of self-monitoring processes that are taught to students when engaging in intercultural communication.	3.62	3.75	4.06	3.56	3.73	HU
17. The teacher motivates students to investigate the cultural values and beliefs that are implied in various forms of communication.	3.81	3.83	4.22	4.00	3.92	HU
18. The teacher employs student-centered tasks in which students construct their own understanding of culture and its role in communication.	3.72	4.00	3.95	4.00	3.85	HU
19. The teacher incorporates independent learning activities, such as research and critical readings, to foster students' individual approaches in addressing linguistic and cultural disparities, which are clearly observed in the teaching process.	3.67	3.47	3.89	4.00	3.71	HU
Composite Mean	3.79	3.83	4.14	3.92	3.88	HU
Legend:	Mean Interval	Verbal Interpretation (VI)				
	4.21 - 5.00	Very Highly Utilized (VHU)		C1 - College 1		
	3.41 - 4.20	Highly Utilized (HU)		C2 - College 2		
	2.61-3.40	Moderately Utilized (MU)		C3 - College 3		
	1.81-2.60	Less Utilized (LU)		C4 - College 4		
	1.00 - 1.81	Not Utilized (NU)				

Table 1.4

Level of Utilization of Responsive Teaching Strategies Among the Marinduque State College Faculty in terms of Discourse

Indicators	Level of Utilization				Total Mean	VI
	College 1	College 2	College 3	College 4		
1. The teacher encourages active participation and involvement of students using discourse techniques.	3.91	4.06	4.33	4.00	4.03	HU
2. The teacher encourages fair and culturally inclusive methods of communication. Use of inclusive language that avoids biases, slang, or expressions that discriminate against groups of people based on race, gender, socioeconomic status, ability, and other identities. Ensuring all students have a voice and feel included.	3.93	4.20	4.06	4.00	4.02	HU
3. The teacher offers frameworks that facilitate scholarly discourse.	3.44	3.56	4.33	3.67	3.67	HU
4. The teacher offers students the chance to enhance their linguistic proficiency.	3.71	4.00	4.11	3.89	3.87	HU
5. The teacher facilitates students' engagement with individuals possessing diverse communication styles.	3.91	3.95	4.11	3.78	3.95	HU
6. The teacher advises students to customize messages based on the specific characteristics of their audience.	3.70	3.92	4.17	3.89	3.86	HU
Composite Mean	3.78	3.95	4.19	3.87	3.91	HU
Legend:	Mean Interval	Verbal Interpretation (VI)				
	4.21 - 5.00	Very Highly Utilized (VHU)				
	3.41 - 4.20	Highly Utilized (HU)				
	2.61-3.40	Moderately Utilized (MU)				
	1.81-2.60	Less Utilized (LU)				

Table 1.5

Level of Utilization of Responsive Teaching Strategies Among Marinduque State College Faculty in terms of Assessment Practices

Indicators	Level of Utilization				Total Mean	VI
	Colleg e 1	Colleg e 2	Colleg e 3	Colleg e 4		
1. The teacher employs formative assessment techniques that yield continuous insights into the comprehension of each student throughout the lesson.	3.98	3.83	4.00	3.11	3.87	HU
2. The teacher requires students to showcase their comprehension through a diverse range of methods.	3.78	4.06	3.89	3.78	3.86	HU
3. The teacher employs regular authentic assessments to evaluate students' proficiency in both language and content like project-based assessments, portfolios, presentations, and real-world problem-solving tasks.	3.82	4.06	3.78	3.44	3.82	HU
4. The teacher employs students to facilitate self-assessment opportunities.	3.94	4.06	3.72	3.56	3.88	HU
Composite Mean	3.88	4.00	3.85	3.47	3.86	HU

Legend:

Mean Interval	Verbal Interpretation (VI)
4.21 - 5.00	Very Highly Utilized (VHU)
3.41 - 4.20	Highly Utilized (HU)
2.61-3.40	Moderately Utilized (MU)
1.81-2.60	Less Utilized (LU)
1.00 - 1.81	Not Utilized (NU)

Table 1.6

Summary Table of the Level of Utilization of Responsive Teaching Strategies of the Marinduque State College Purposive Communication Faculty in the Five Domains

Domain	Composite Mean	Description	Rank
1. Curriculum Design	4.06	Highly Utilized	1.5
2. Classroom Relationships	4.06	Highly Utilized	1.5
3. Instructional Practices	3.97	Highly Utilized	3
4. Discourse	3.88	Highly Utilized	5
5. Assessment Practices	3.91	Highly Utilized	4
Grand Mean	3.98	Highly Utilized	

Legend:

Mean Interval	Verbal Interpretation (VI)
4.21 - 5.00	Very Highly Utilized (VHU)
3.41 - 4.20	Highly Utilized (HU)

2.61-3.40 Moderately Utilized (MU)
 1.81-2.60 Less Utilized (LU)
 1.00 - 1.81 Not Utilized (NU)

II. Differences of Level of Utilization of Responsive Teaching Strategies of Marinduque State College

Table 2.1

Statistical Table Showing the Significant Difference on the Level of Utilization of Responsive Teaching Strategies of Marinduque State College Purposive Communication Faculty

Domains	Grouping Variable	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Curriculum Design	Colleges 1	0.836	Not Significant	Do not reject Ho
Classroom Relationships	- 4	0.892		
Instructional Practices		0.694		
Discourse		0.756		
Assessment Practices		0.618		

Table 2.2

Result of Test of Difference on the Level of Utilization of Responsive Teaching Strategies by the Purposive Communication Faculty in Selected Colleges Across Domains (Culturally Responsive Indicators)

ANOVA							
Mean	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Between Groups	.274	4	.069	0.601	0.664	Not significant	Do not reject Ho
Within Groups	5.136	45	.114				
Total	5.410	49					

III. Level of Cultural Communicative Competence of Marinduque State College Students in terms of Cultural Knowledge and Cultural Skills

Table 3.1

Level of Cultural Communicative Competence of Marinduque State College Students in Terms of Cultural Knowledge and Cultural Skills (Based on Cultural Test)

• Items	College 1		College 2		College 3		College 4		Total	
	F	MPS %	MPS %	D						
<u>Cultural Knowledge</u>										
1. Students recognize the respecting key values, behaviors, and customs that are important within that culture.	96	64	11	9	24	41	11	28	35.50	AM
2. Students contrast important aspects of the host language and culture with others.	69	46	45	36	37	64	19	48	48.50	AM
3. Students contrast his/her own behaviors with those of the hosts in important areas.	75	50	29	23	46	79	8	20	43.00	AM
4. Students cite important historical and socio-political factors that shape his/her own & host culture.	64	43	42	34	36	62	28	70	52.25	AM
5. Students describe interactional behaviors common among others culture in social and professional areas.	44	29	109	88	43	74	25	63	63.50	AM
6. Students discuss and contrast various behavioral patterns in his/her own culture with those in others culture.	60	40	112	90	42	72	30	75	69.25	MTM
7. Students cite a definition of culture and describe its components and complexities.	79	53	98	79	34	59	21	53	61.00	AM
8. Students recognize signs of culture stress and some strategies for overcoming it.	70	47	91	73	38	66	22	55	60.25	AM
9. Students know some techniques to aid his/her learning of the host language & culture.	57	38	34	27	18	31	12	30	31.50	LM
10. Students describe a model of cross-cultural adjustment stages.	54	36	113	91	48	83	26	65	68.75	MTM
11. Students cite various learning processes & strategies for learning about and adjusting to the host culture.	66	44	115	93	49	84	25	63	71.00	MTM
Mean		45		58		65		52	54.95	AM
<u>Cultural Skills</u>										
1. Students demonstrate flexibility when interacting with persons from the host culture.	53	35	45	36	53	91	18	45	51.75	AM
2. Students adjust behavior, dress, etc. as appropriate to avoid offending the host.	81	54	91	73	41	71	19	48	61.50	AM
3. Students has the ability to contrast the host culture with his own.	75	50	98	79	48	83	23	58	67.50	MTM
4. Students use strategies for learning the host language and culture.	92	61	117	94	51	88	26	65	77.00	MTM
5. Students demonstrate a capacity to interact appropriately in a variety of	33	22	35	28	43	74	15	38	40.50	AM

different social situations.

6. Students use appropriate strategies for adapting to host culture.	87	58	113	91	39	67	28	70	71.50	MTM
7. Students used culture-specific information to improve my style and personal interaction.	96	64	113	91	36	62	27	68	71.25	MTM
8. Students helped to resolve cross-cultural conflicts and misunderstandings when they arose.	93	62	112	90	37	64	19	48	66.00	MTM
Mean		51	73	75		55	63.38	AM		
GRAND MEAN		48%	66%	70%		54%	59.17	AM		
<i>Legend:</i>	<i>Mean Percentage Score (MPS)</i>	<i>Description</i>		<i>Mean Percentage Score (MPS)</i>		<i>Description (D)</i>				
	96%-100%	<i>Mastered (M)</i>		16%-34%		<i>Low Mastery (LM)</i>				
	86%-95%	<i>Closely Approximating to Mastery (CAM)</i>		5%-15%		<i>Very Low Mastery (VLM)</i>				
	66%-85%	<i>Moving Towards Mastery (MTM)</i>		0%-4%		<i>Absolutely No Mastery (ANM)</i>				
	35%-65%	<i>Average Mastery (AM)</i>								

Table 3.2

Level of Cultural Communicative Competence of Marinduque State College Students in Terms of Cultural Knowledge and Cultural Skills (Based on Cultural Log)

Items	Colleg	Colleg	Colleg	Colleg	Total	
	e 1 MS	e 2 MS	e 3 MS	e 4 MS	MS	D
Cultural Knowledge						
1. Students understand the host culture's norms and taboos, compare their language and behavior to your own, and contrast your own actions with theirs in crucial areas.	1.64	1.50	2.13	2.21	1.87	B
2. Students discuss the historical and socio-political factors that influence one's culture, common social and professional behaviors, and the definition and complexities of culture.	1.55	1.63	2.10	2.05	1.83	B
3. Students identify signs of culture stress and provide strategies for overcoming it, as well as learn techniques to facilitate language and culture learning.	1.61	1.61	2.17	1.82	1.80	B
4. Students provide a model of cross-cultural adjustment stages and discusses various learning processes and strategies for understanding and adapting to a host culture.	1.67	1.80	2.10	1.87	1.86	B
Mean	1.62	1.64	2.13	1.99	1.84	B
Cultural Skills						
1. Students effectively interact with others culture, demonstrate flexibility, adjust behavior, contrast with the host culture, and use strategies for learning the language and culture.	1.52	1.65	2.47	1.71	1.84	B
2. Students demonstrate appropriate social interaction, adapt strategies to host culture, and utilize culture-specific information to enhance personal interaction and style.	1.52	1.65	2.30	1.71	1.80	B
3. Students utilize cultural-specific information to	1.46	1.35	2.23	1.58	1.6	L

enhance personal interactions and resolved cross-cultural conflicts and misunderstandings.						6	
	Mean	1.50	1.55	2.33	1.67	1.76	B
GRAND MEAN		1.56	1.60	2.23	1.83	1.80	B

Legend:

<i>Mean Score (MS) Interval</i>	<i>Description (D)</i>
3.25 – 4.00	Exemplary (E)
2.50 – 3.24	Proficient (P)
1.75 – 2.49	Basic (B)
1.00 – 1.74	Limited (L)

IV. Differences on the Level of Cultural Communicative Competence of Marinduque State College Students

Table 4.1.1

Multiple Comparisons on the Level of Cultural Communicative Competence (Cultural Test) of Marinduque State College Students in the Four Selected Colleges

Domain	Multiple Comparisons		p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Cultural Knowledge	College 1	College 2	0.000	Significant	Reject Ho
		College 3			
		College 4	0.991	Not Significant	
	College 2	College 3	0.001	Significant	
		College 4	0.000		
College 3	College 4		Significant		
Cultural Skills	College 1	College 2	0.000	Significant	
		College 3			
		College 4	0.621	Not Significant	
	College 2	College 3	0.425		
		College 4	0.000	Significant	
	College 3	College 4			

Table 4.1.2

Multiple Comparisons on the Level of Cultural Communicative Competence (Cultural Log) of Marinduque State College Students in the Four Selected Colleges

Domain	Multiple Comparisons		p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Cultural Knowledge	College 1	College 2	0.998	Not Significant	Reject Ho
		College 3	0.000	Significant	
		College 4	0.006		
	College 2	College 3	0.005		
		College 4	0.052	Not Significant	
	College 3	College 4	0.800		
Cultural Skills	College 1	College 2	0.965		Significant
		College 3	0.000	Significant	
		College 4	0.478	Not Significant	
	College 2	College 3	0.000	Significant	
		College 4	0.846	Not Significant	
	College 3	College 4	0.000	Significant	

Table 4.2

Result of Test of Difference on Cultural Knowledge and Cultural Skills (Cultural Communicative Competence) of Students from Selected Colleges

	ANOVA			F	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square				
Between Groups	.681	1	.681	29.136	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Within Groups	12.105	518	.023				
Total	12.786	519					

V. Relationship on the Level of Utilization of Responsive Teaching Strategies of Marinduque State College Purposive Communication Teachers and Level of Cultural Communicative Competence of Marinduque State College Students

Table 5

Result of Test of Relationship Between the Level of Utilization of Responsive Teaching Strategies of Marinduque State College Purposive Communication Teachers and Level of Cultural Communicative Competence of Marinduque State College Students

			Domain	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Teachers' Utilization of Responsive Teaching	Level of	of	Cultural Test	.221	Not Significant	Do not reject Ho

VI. Problems Encountered and Interventions Conducted by the Marinduque State College Faculty in the Utilization of Responsive Teaching Strategies

Table 6

Problems Encountered and Intervention Conducted by the Marinduque State College Faculty in the Utilization of Responsive Teaching Strategies

THEME	Problems Encountered	Intervention Conducted
1. Fostering positive and inclusive learning environment	Lack of being valued and heard due to classroom relationships. Students feel lack of confidence and anxious. Setting limitations Conflict management	Inclusive learning environment Valuing opinions Active Listening Non-judgmental environment Setting Expectations Supportive atmosphere Building rapport
2. Diverse student learning styles	Lack of strategies to support different learning styles.	Promoting Open-mindedness Positive Reinforcement Identifying weakness Strengthening emotional intelligence
3. Online learning modality	Poor internet connectivity Lack of student engagement	Contextualized-Based Learning
4. Language barrier	Low English-speaking skills Low self-esteem	Create varied language learning and speaking experiences Flexible Classroom Discussion Contextualized-Based Learning
5. Teacher flexibility	Inadequacy of Adaptability to the language learning interventions appropriate to learners Diversified Classroom Culture	Technology Adaptation Collaborative Teaching and Learning Activities

VII. Proposed Curriculum Framework Aligns with United Nation Sustainable Development Goals

Figure 1. Proposed Enhanced Curriculum Framework

1. Fostering Positive and Inclusive Learning Environment

There are four (4) sub-themes that emerged from this theme. The first sub-theme found is focused on **ensuring that students are valued and heard**.

According to R10: "...naniniwala kasi ako na, 'yong pagkatuto ng estudyante, o mas matututo ang mga estudyante if they feel valued if pinapakinggan din ang kanilang mga opinions." In order to create an intervention for this problem, according to the respondent,

it is necessary to have a **supportive environment** to make the students feel comfortable during the discussion as they find it to make the class more engaging and participative for everyone. As per R4: "... 'yong una ko pong pa-ano sa kanila, 'kumusta kayo?' ang mga sagot nila ay 'I'm okay, ma'am' 'I'm good' 'I'm fine'".

Some of the respondents said that **building rapport** is also important so they could set their minds to the lesson. According to R3, "...I'm trying to do is build a learning environment sa kanila pero also I set limitations with them para alam nila kung hanggang kailan lamang." This is true with R2 who said, "So syempre, aside from in the beginning, lagi naman nating pinapag-introduce 'yong mga estudyante natin, so during the classroom, ayon ine-encourage natin na sumagot sila at i-honor 'yong mga sagot nila.'" And R3 who attested that "... I usually start with asking my students how their day so far, talking with them informally before starting the discussion...I try to use encouraging words to them halimbawa parang nahihiya na sila na sumagot."

Moreover, **regular feedback** is one of the interventions suggested by the respondents that emerged from the FGD to attain a positive learning environment to create a positive and inclusive learning environment for the students. According to R4, "...after po ng klase is, providing timely feedback po, and ayon, maintain feedback po from our students...kailangan improve doon sa ine-employ mo sa kanila na strategy." This is supported by R6 who said, "...nagbibigay rin po ako ng feedbacks sa kanila, to ensure na alam nila kung saan po sila nagkulang,.. 'Yong mga handle kong students, very open naman po sila in receiving feedback na binibigay ko."

Another sub theme under the first problem that emerged is **lack of confidence and anxiety of students**. As per R2, "...Meron talagang tunganga lang sa klase... so kapag gano'n, hinahayaan ko na lang sila kasi mas marami pa rin naman 'yong nagparticipate, 'yong nakikinig sa klase ko." Additionally, R1 said that, "...kaya nga lang kahit ung iba asagutan ka ng isang line lamang, isang phrase so mejo mataas pa ung kanilang apprehension na baka ung sabihin nila ay mali, or baka ung iba ay pagtawanan sila. Meron silang mga fears.". According to Young (1991), learners need to adopt attitudes and strategies that pay off in terms of low anxiety, high motivation, and ultimately in the ability to convey information and communicate ideas and feelings. This is one of the challenges in second language teaching – to provide students with a learner-centered, low-anxiety classroom environment. In order to address this, some of the respondents cited that they implement **interactive and collaborative learning environment**. As per R4, "I also employ po team building activities na makakapag-build para mas makakapag-build ng kanilang samahan." This is the same with R1 who said, "...so kahit hindi sila magsalita or magexpress orally pero during brainstorming nakakapagsalita na sila doon or nakakapagexpress na sila sa kapwa nila estudyante, so somehow naencourage na magsalita although na hindi na mukhang presentation type ...little by little sa mga brainstorming activities, hopefully nakakapagexpress sila orally." Part of collaborative learning is the conduct of **peer collaboration** to help students overcome their anxiety of speaking. Like what R4 said, "Ine-encourage ko rin po ang peer collaboration and creating force in a non-judgmental atmosphere, which allows my students to comfortable practice and find their discussion skills."

The third sub theme is **setting of limitations**. According to R3: *“In building positive climate or learning environment with them, ang nagiging problema ay nagkakameron ng minsan sumusobra.”* As per Gay (2010), without culturally responsive teaching education can never be the best it should be for students who are not part of the majority and mainstream of schools and society. Setting limitations is very important so students would know their boundaries and would foster respect among the students and the teacher. With this, according to the respondents, it is very important to **set expectations** so that the students are guided with how they should act and what they are intended to do during class discussions. It was emphasized by some of the respondents that setting expectations among students is very important so that they are aware of what is expected from them by the end of the lesson and by the end of the course. According to R3, *“I set clear expectations with the students’ kung sila ay somewhat reluctant sa mga class participations po. Parang ang ginagawa ko na lang ay, yun nga nagvavary ako ng mga questioning techniques and asks for feedback.”* According to McKinley (2010), teachers should not see themselves as sources of knowledge and regard students as ‘tabula rasa’ for which they set expectations for students to know what is expected of them.

The fourth sub-theme is **conflict management**. According to R4, *“...Sometimes po, bina-balance ko po ‘yong mga needs ng students ko.”* In order to address these, based on the respondents, it is important for them to be **open minded and to value the opinion** of each of the students so that they would feel that they are part of the class regardless of their backgrounds. According to R4, *“I’m also encouraging po open communication, active listening, and yong pag-value po ng kanilang mga opinions during our discussions, na I think makakapag-contribute sa pagkakaroon ng very supportive atmosphere.”*

3. Diverse Student Learning Styles

Another emerging theme that arose from thematic analysis, is **diverse student learning styles**. According to R6: *“...,lagi akong nagpapa-activity po like essay and other activity po para malaman kung ano ‘yong weakness nila and ayon nga, ‘yong iba gets agad, ‘yong iba kailangan ko pa paulit-ulitin po,... so ina-adapt ko po kung ano ‘yong mas okay, ano ‘yong sa tingin ko ‘yong makakatulong sa kanila para ma-overcome ‘yong gano’ng hindrance pagdating sa pag-understand nila ng lesson.”* This is confirmed by R2. According to R2, *“... na merong active, merong kahit i-encourage mo sila na mag-participate, talagang hindi mo sila nakikitaan ng participation. So siguro nga dahil iba iba rin ‘yong level of activeness ng mga estudyante natin. ...i-consider ano ano ‘yong kaibahan ng mga estudyante natin when giving activities.”* Moreover, R1 explained that *“...May mga learners na okay yung sagot kapag written activity kesa ung oral na palaging magaraise ng hand. Kumbaga mas makikilala mo ung mga students base sa kung sino ung sagot ng sagot.”* The respondents stated that the classroom must employ **good and active listening skills** so that everyone would feel heard likewise the teacher must also have good listening skills so they would understand and comprehend what the students are saying. As per R4, *“I provide explicit guidelines on active listening and respectful communication, since ito po, ‘yong subject nila ay purposive communication.”* This is supported by R6, *“pagdating po sa pagkaklase so same with R4, active listening po is a must pagdating po sa mga students.”* While implementing a good listening skill, the respondents also reiterated that having a **non-judgmental environment** and having an

open mind is pivotal in **promoting inclusivity**. According to R6, “Aside from that, lagi ko pong binabanggit sa kanila ‘yong avoiding bullying and disrespecting, hindi sila pwede sa klase ko... lagi ko rin po silang chine-check before mag-start ang klase, kinukumusta ko sila, at least alam ko on how to approach them.”

The same thoughts were shared by R3, “...Let the students feel that you are open with their every answer, so kung halimbawa na merong contrasting issues or meron silang iba ibang viewpoints so ang ginagawa ko na lang... And was followed up by R6, “...creating a safe environment po kung saan all the students po feel safe, and when expressing their opinions without the fear na ma-judge po.” Another intervention suggested by the respondents is **acknowledgment and positive reinforcement**. According to the respondents, these are important so that students would feel **valued and accepted** in the class. As per R6, “yong positive enforcement, ‘yong acknowledgment po, I always acknowledge po ‘yong kanilang gawa, ‘yong activities nila.” This was explained further by R3 that, “may mga bata kasi na ung learning style nila, they are just hesitant, or they are just shy...kung sino lang ung nasa likod, kung sino ung parang space out na mga estudyante sila ung tinatanong ko. Magugulat ka minsan sila ung may malalalim na thoughts dun sa itinuturo.”

Another interesting intervention that emerged from the FGD is the **strengthening of the emotional intelligence** of the students. As observed from the responses, some also reiterated the importance of considering not only the intellect of the students but also their emotional intelligence. This is necessary to foster the holistic development of students. According to R6, “first step ko po kasi lagi ay to identify their weaknesses. ‘Yon talaga. Ina-identify ko po ‘yong weakness nila, then I’m going to look for something, strategy po na sa tingin ko matututo po sila and mai-improve po ang weakness nila, at the same time, mage-enjoy po ‘yong bata.” Additionally, R2 cited, “i-highlight na kailangan natin i-consider ano ano ‘yong kaibahan ng mga estudyante natin when giving activities.” Aside from **identifying their weaknesses**, one of the respondents also shared her practice of **motherly approach**. According to R5, “lagi kong inaparamdam sa kanila na ‘yong approach ko ay motherly kasi sa ganoong paraan, alam ko na nagiging kumportable po sila, ... ‘wag silang matatakot na i-showcase ‘yong kanilang strengths and weaknesses and I always let them feel na ‘yong every effort na ine-exert nila ay well-appreciated po.”

4. Online Learning Modality

Based on the FGD, all the respondents attest to encountering problems when conducting online classes. One of the sub themes found is **poor internet connectivity**. According to R4: “Actually, Ma’am Jessica, when it comes to sa online klase namin, alam naman po natin na isa sa, kumbaga parang nagiging hadlang is the internet connection.” Additionally, most common problem discussed was the **lack of active student engagement** during online discussions. According to R4: “...iba po kasi ‘yong nakikita mo rin ‘yong facial expressions nila, depende na lang...hindi pa rin po sapat ‘yong basta lang nakikita mo ‘yong ganiyang hitsura nila, if during the discussion, ‘yong engagement nila, unlike sa face to face ...”. Moreover, R6 added, “Siguro kung titingnan po natin, yes, actually sa online, ang hirap kasi po ‘yong mga bata, ang dami talaga nilang ginagawa, na hindi lang po sila basta nakikinig. Kapag face to face po kasi, super active talaga po ng mga bata, tapos pagdating sa online, ayan, may times na ang tatahimik na.” This is the same with the

statement of R2 that, *“Iba rin kapag face to face kaya I really opt in my class sa purposive communication, face to face kami kasi kapag online, alam mo ‘yon...hindi ko alam kung nandoon pa ba sila sa platform, kung nakikinig pa ba sila...”* According to R6, *“Since sabi ko nga po ang hilig kong mag-adapt ng current trends na gustong-gusto ng mga bata ‘yong mga activities na interactive talaga, na ‘yong mga nakikita nila sa tiktok, sa twitter, sa facebook, kumbaga ginagamit ko po ‘yon to apply ‘yong mga natututunan namin.”*

5. Language Barrier

However, despite considering English as the second language in the Philippines, many students still **struggle understanding and performing English** in a conversational context. This is true among the observations of the respondents. According to R6, *“Medyo hirap din po sila, actually, sa english, which is totoo po na hirap po ...tulungan sila to improve their english speaking skills, kasi nga english is very important pagdating sa business context kasi ‘yon po ang language ng mga bata.”* According to R2, *“...‘yong mga examples ko ay something na related talaga sa kanila. Like for example mga electrical technology students yong mga example ko may kinalaman sa kung ano usually ‘yong ginagawa nila... ‘yong mga pagaayos ng circuit, ng electrical circuit, paggawa ng mga instruction, pagbigay ng mga instruction, mga gano’n.”* She explained further that, *“kailangan ‘yong mga examples natin in class is ‘yong magiging relatable para sa kanila para they feel involved... kumbaga para merong inclusivity talaga in class...”* This is the same with R1 who handles students with same field of expertise. According to her, *“as much as possible I try to ask them to give examples kunwari sa mga electrical ganyan, ...I try to ask them examples na type of communication or processes na typically naobeserve nila pag nagakutingting ng mga circuits o sa mga major subjects nila.”* Moreover, this was supported by R5, *“lagi akong nagabigay ng mga examples na based sa totoong buhay kasi sa subject kasi hindi dapat laging theories, dapat more on application... but also sa buhay nila. Kumbaga, lagi akong nagabigay ng examples based sa totoong buhay para at least mas mavisualize nila ung nasabi ko o nadiscuss ko.”*

6. Teacher Flexibility

The last emerging theme identified during the FGD is **teacher flexibility** which is categorized into two (2) subthemes. The first subtheme is **adaptability**. Given that Purposive Communication is a core subject which should be integrated among all courses, language teachers from a particular college in MSC are given Purposive Communication teaching load among varying colleges. This was found to be a challenge among them as it is necessary for them to be flexible enough to recraft their syllabus aligned to the field of expertise of the class that they are handling. According to R2: *“Actually, ngayon lang ulit ako nag-handle ng purposive communication after how many years. The last time na nagturo ako ng subject na ito was before sa engineering pa, before pandemic pa ‘yon. And this is again my first time after pandemic.”* This is supported by R7 who said: *“Sa mga problem that I encounter po, siguro po somehow...so malaking adjustment po for me kasi magkaiba po ung culture po sa engineering students at sa industrial technology students.”* Another subtheme found was **classroom culture**. Some of the teacher’s experienced the feeling of outcast to the classroom as the students know each other already. Being new inside the classroom, it takes a lot of adjustment to build and establish a positive learning environment between them and among the students

especially if they are in their second year in the college. According to R3: “...I think every semester akong may hawak na Purposive Communication. I think one of the problems is adjusting with the classroom culture of the students... I try to adapt and observe their different personalities, or culture na meron ang mga estudyante. Kasi usually I cannot fathom on what they are thinking when I’m discussing.”

DISCUSSION

In terms of the level of utilization of responsive teaching strategies among the Marinduque State College faculty (Part I) indicates the extent of inclusive and flexible teaching approaches to ensure that all faculty members are effectively implementing responsive teaching strategies to meet the diverse needs of their students. The process of designing a curriculum for cultural communicative competence entails integrating Intercultural Communicative Competence (ICC) into language curricula. This integration aims to assist students in cultivating an understanding and admiration for the language and culture they are studying, as well as fostering an awareness of their own culture. Additionally, it equips students with the necessary skills to effectively communicate and adapt in various cultural settings.

Table 1.1 indicates the level of utilization of responsive teaching strategies among the Marinduque State College faculty in terms of curriculum design. **Table 1.1** illustrates the level of utilization of responsive teaching strategies among the Marinduque State College faculty in terms of *Curriculum Design* with ten indicators of responsive teaching strategies pertaining to curriculum design. These indicators encompass a wide array of elements, including the integration of significant issues, the challenging of stereotypes, the facilitation of diverse viewpoints, the addressing of intercultural communication, the focus on cultural diversity, the delineation of learning outcomes, the prioritization of intercultural awareness, and the fostering of communication skills. The basis utilized by the evaluators includes the course syllabus utilized by the faculty. The data revealed that indicator 10 has the highest level of utilization of 4.20 that indicates the teacher effectively incorporates specific intercultural and global learning outcomes and objectives into the curriculum, clearly detailing in the course syllabus.

Particularly, as the evaluation were conducted in the classroom observation the course syllabus of the faculty includes objectives and activities that address significant classroom, school, and community issues that focus on local issues and community projects applying their learning to real-world contexts and problems.

On the other hand, the lowest level of utilization is indicator 9 having the mean of 3.93 that indicates that the teacher's course syllabus includes high utilization of diverse instructional activities aimed at enhancing students' communication skills in multicultural and multilingual environments. Hence, the course syllabus among the faculty highly incorporates a range of instructional activities, ensuring a rich and varied learning experience through role-plays, group discussions, language practice sessions, and

cultural studies. This variety caters to different learning styles and keeps students engaged. Overall, the composite mean highlights the total mean score for all indicators across all colleges, which stands at 4.06, indicating highly utilized of responsive teaching practices connected to curriculum design. This indicates a positive trend in the application of responsive teaching practices at Marinduque State College, but with variances among metrics and institutions.

As a result, the findings show that faculty members use responsive teaching practices extensively, particularly when designing curricula. This active participation demonstrates a proactive commitment to incorporate important problems such as various perspectives and cultural diversity. Variances in implementation among departments indicate areas for focused interventions and the sharing of best practices. While the general trend is encouraging, there is room for improvement, indicating the importance of continued monitoring and support to increase teaching effectiveness. However, during the classroom observation, the evaluators noted that the teachers did not follow budget time allocation of contents in instruction indicated in the course syllabus due to school activities and other designations of faculty. This further created inconsistencies in the implementation of the instruction.

Therefore, the need for alternative strategies for class instruction among the teachers is imperative to meet the competencies needed of the course through blended learning. The findings support the study of Rodriguez (2019) in which he explored the integration of responsive teaching strategies into curriculum design within the institution, emphasizing the alignment of curriculum goals with student needs and interests through flexible instructional frameworks. Moreover, Santos and Cruz (2018), emphasized the alignment of curriculum goals with industry demands and student needs through adaptable instructional frameworks. On the other hand, Sherrington (2022) stated that in responsive teaching, practice exercises and instructional materials are modified in real-time in response to students' success and confidence levels. To do this, time allotment must be set forth for each stage of the learning sequence, including modeling, elucidating learning objectives, guided practice, and individual practice.

Overall, the findings highlight the significance of responsive teaching strategies and the necessity for ongoing efforts to promote their effective implementation. Classroom relationships in cultural communicative competences, emphasize the importance of creating a learning environment that fosters intercultural understanding and effective communication.

Table 1.2 presents the level of utilization of responsive teaching strategies among Marinduque State College's faculty, with a specific focus on *Classroom Relationships*. **Table 1.2** presents the level of utilization of responsive teaching strategies among Marinduque State College faculty in terms of Classroom Relationships. The indicators comprise various aspects such as fostering respect, promoting collaboration, and setting high expectations. Mean scores across colleges and composite means indicate a generally high level of utilization, with all indicators falling within the "Highly Utilized" range. Notably, indicator 1 has the highest mean of 4.08 and College 3 which has a total mean of 4.17 shows the highest utilization (Highly Utilized). The teacher exemplifies an

ethos of compassion, characterized by fair and inclusive relationships and a sense of connection through asking motivational questions “How are you?”, “Are you okay?”, etc. This creates strong connection among teacher and student relationship that builds rapport in teaching and learning. On the other hand, indicator 2 which has a total mean of 3.81 (Highly Utilized) and College 2 has a lower mean of 3.86 and a total mean of 3.81. This particularly conveys that teacher have elevated expectations for every student. Thus, the classroom observation indicated some teachers do not give more of expectations since students are being pressured and this affects the productivity of the students.

Hence, the composite value of 3.97 (Highly Utilized) demonstrates widespread use of responsive teaching practices throughout the institution. This points to a positive trend of building inclusive and collaborative educational environments. However, discrepancies between metrics and colleges reveal possible areas for development or targeted intervention. Overall, the findings emphasize the importance of responsive teaching practices in improving classroom interactions and identify areas for additional improvement. Therefore, the data show a good trend in the use of responsive teaching practices, implying that these strategies should be actively implemented in classrooms to create respect, promote collaboration, and establish high expectations.

While overall utilization is good, discrepancies between metrics and colleges show the importance of tailored efforts to achieve cultural communicative competence. The broad use of responsive teaching approaches throughout the school demonstrates attempts to foster inclusive and collaborative learning environments. Specifically, teachers’ utilization of reflective questions build rapport among the students. The identification of areas for development underlines the importance of continual improvement and ongoing support to enable successful implementation.

The findings support the study of Smith and Jones (2020) wherein they explored the role of classroom relationships in facilitating responsive teaching, highlighting the importance of cultivating a supportive learning environment characterized by trust and open communication between faculty and students, which positively impacts student motivation and academic achievement. Similarly, Garcia and Santos (2020) and Reyes and Garcia (2019) highlight the significance of positive teacher-student relationships that are characterized by trust, respect, and open communication. Moreover, learning about students’ backgrounds, interests, and cultural identities build meaningful connections. This will help students incorporate cultural knowledge and experiences into lessons and activities to make content more relevant and engaging.

Developing an inclusive curriculum that represents diverse backgrounds and perspectives, rather than just the dominant culture would help foster a supportive, respectful classroom environment where differences are celebrated. The level of utilization of responsive teaching strategies among the Marinduque State College faculty in terms of *instructional practices* is presented in Table 6.3. Instructional practices are strategies that emphasize the development of self-awareness, openness, and transformation as crucial elements of intercultural competence.

As such, **Table 1.3** presents the level of utilization of responsive teaching strategies among the Marinduque State College in terms of Instructional Practices. The table includes 19 indicators that cover a wide range of topics, from tailored instruction to intercultural communication management. Mean scores across four colleges (C1, C2, C3, C4) are used to assess utilization levels. Indicator 6 has the highest mean of 4.01 which means the teacher highly utilizes audio-visual materials, including films, slides, and podcasts, to enhance communication by introducing linguistic and cultural diversity. On the other hand, the lowest mean among the indicators (were) is indicator 14, the teacher makes use of activities for perspective taking in managing communication incorporated in the classroom activities, having the mean of 3.68. Particularly, teachers were utilizing open ended questions that incorporated with real life contexts that help students be open, share information, and display trust between other communicators. These behavioral cues indicate that individuals are considering each other's viewpoints.

However, some students were not very expressive on their opinion due to their language barrier. This hinders active participation among students in the classroom discussion. The composite means of 3.88 (Highly Utilized) indicates extensive use of responsive teaching strategies for instructional practices. This highlights a favorable trend among Marinduque State College teachers in creating student-centered, culturally sensitive educational techniques, while also identifying areas for possible improvement. Therefore, the findings provide important insights into the faculty's adoption of responsive teaching strategies, with a specific emphasis on instructional practices.

Notably, indications in the "Highly Utilized" category show broad adoption of responsive teaching methodologies throughout the institution, implying active integration of personalized education and intercultural communication management into teaching practices. Teachers utilized digital instructional materials like videos and podcasts, and etc, since they are the most accessible in online mode of learning that is common among all students. Thus, the emphasis on diversity and cultural sensitivity needs to be highlighted as significant in encouraging inclusivity in educational methods. Particularly, they utilized videos that are bias free presented in different context.

Overall, the findings point to a favorable trend toward student-centered and culturally sensitive instructional techniques, which are consistent with current pedagogical approaches that value student engagement and diversity. This shows the institution's commitment to using responsive teaching practices and indicate particular areas for development, with the goal of improving student teaching and learning experiences. The study supports the findings of Rasul et al. (2011) that the use of audio-visual aids can increase learning by helping to arouse and sustain interest, present information in a variety of ways, and allow for the transfer of knowledge and skill to new tasks. Therefore, it has effective way to enhance communication, introduce linguistic and cultural diversity, and develop cultural communicative competence. The use of visuals, accompanied by appropriate audio input, can help students focus, pay attention, learn new words, and improve memory retention. Moreover, Brown and Li (2017) explored how digital tools can facilitate cultural understanding and enhance communication skills among students from diverse backgrounds. This emphasizes that digital literacy skills, such as evaluating digital information and communicating effectively online, are essential for developing cultural

competence. This includes understanding how digital platforms can be used to share and learn about different cultures. Garcia et al. (2019) investigated the utilization of responsive instructional practices, identifying cooperative learning, problem-based learning, and flipped classroom approaches as effective strategies to accommodate diverse learning styles and promote deeper understanding among students. By exposing students to a variety of linguistic, cultural, and media representations, audio-visual materials can help broaden their perspectives and cultural knowledge. The interactive and engaging nature of audio-visuals may better facilitate language learning and communication skills development compared to traditional lecture-based instruction.

Thoughtfully selecting audio-visual resources that reflect diverse backgrounds and experiences can create a more inclusive classroom culture. Cole and Padgett (2018), on the other hand, focused on perspective-taking exercises in social studies classrooms. Their research highlighted how crucial it is to introduce pupils to historical events via the perspectives of those who were there. By pushing students to take into account different viewpoints, these techniques not only improve their historical knowledge but also help them become more culturally competent. By including these exercises in the curriculum, teachers can greatly improve their students' cross-cultural communication skills.

Further, Martinez et al. (2020) explored and supported also that identifying active learning and problem-based approaches are effective strategies to promote critical thinking among engineering students. Following that year, Martinez et al. (2021) added that active learning and problem-based approaches in promoting critical thinking are common also among industrial technology students. The level of utilization of responsive teaching strategies among the Marinduque State College faculty in terms of discourse is presented in Table 1. 4. Discourse is essential for cultural communicative competence as it mirrors the cultural knowledge, patterns, and norms that dictate acceptable language use and communication in various cultural settings.

Table 1.4 presents the level of utilization of responsive teaching strategies focusing specifically on discourse. The table includes six indicators that address topics such as student participation, cultural inclusivity, academic discourse facilitation, linguistic competency enhancement, and engagement with multiple communication methods. Mean ratings from four institutions and a composite mean are used to assess utilization levels, which are all in the "Highly Utilized" range. The composite means of 3.91 suggests that responsive teaching practices connected to discourse are widely used (highly utilized) throughout the institution. Notably, Indicator 1 and College 3 get the highest mean score, 4.03 (Highly Utilized) and 4.19 (Highly Utilized), respectively, indicating a strong emphasis on promoting intellectual discourse. This entails that the teacher encourages active participation and involvement of students using discourse techniques. Particularly, teachers use scaffolding technique, establish rapport through questions, fishbowl discussions, and ask for some clarification. On the other hand, Indicator 3 and College 1 has the lowest mean score of 3.67 and 3.78 (Highly Utilized), respectively, indicating space for growth in this area. Particularly, the indicator - teacher offers frameworks that facilitate scholarly discourse is highly utilized but not very highly utilized. Since most of the students enrolled in the second semester are more of under the

category of future skilled workers, students are not more of into reading activities. Their learning styles vary and so their learning needs.

Thus, the findings show a good trend toward promoting effective discourse practices among Marinduque State College teaching members, while also revealing areas for potential improvement. The findings provide a complete review of the adoption of responsive teaching practices among Marinduque State College professors, with focus on discourse. The indicators address a variety of subjects, including student participation, cultural inclusivity, academic discourse facilitation, linguistic competency advancement, and engagement with numerous communication means. Particularly, teachers call students to answer verbally. This engages all students in thinking about the ideas and help them engage in active learning. Thus, there are some students who were not too active in the discussion since they are having hard time to express themselves.

The findings support the study of Smith (2023), that purports creating a positive learning environment is essential for promoting active participation. The study indicates that when students feel safe and valued, they are more likely to engage in discussions and activities. Strategies such as open communication, respect for diverse perspectives, and collaborative learning are crucial for fostering an inclusive atmosphere that enhances cultural communicative competence. Martinez (2021) in which he analyzed the role of discourse in shaping teaching and learning interactions, emphasized the need for faculty development initiatives to foster reflective teaching practices and meaningful discourse in the classroom. Lopez (2018) explored the role of discourse in shaping teaching and learning interactions, emphasizing the importance of fostering meaningful discourse to promote student engagement and critical thinking.

Additionally, Lopez and Cruz (2021) analyzed discourse's role in shaping teaching and learning interactions, emphasizing the importance of fostering a supportive and inclusive learning environment. However, studies by Pacini-Ketchabaw and Schecter (2002) had shown how crucial it is to use frameworks that support academic discourse in the classroom in order to foster the development of cultural communicative competence. Teachers can use frameworks to address language and cultural disparities, highlighting the importance of comprehending different viewpoints in order to improve students' cultural competency. Thus, the study of Da Costa (2021) emphasized that students with limited language proficiency often struggle to express their understanding of concepts, making it difficult for teachers to accurately assess their learning and build rapport that hinders learning effectively.

Table 1.5 presents the level of utilization of responsive teaching strategies Marinduque State College faculty, with (a) focus on *assessment practices*. The table includes four indicators covering various aspects such as formative assessment techniques, diverse assessment methods, regular authentic assessments, and self-assessment opportunities for students. Utilization levels are assessed using mean scores across four colleges and a composite mean. All indicators are within the "Highly Utilized" range. The composite mean of 3.86 shows a high level of use of responsive teaching strategies related to assessment processes throughout the institution. Notably, Indicator 4 and College 2 have the highest mean score of 3.88 (Highly Utilized) and 4.0 (Highly Utilized), respectively,

indicating a considerable emphasis on formative assessment procedures particularly, teacher employs students to facilitate self-assessment opportunities through. They specifically use recitation activities particularly open-ended questions to reflect and assess their own learning in the course. Indicator 3 and College 4 has the lowest mean score of 3.82 (Highly Utilized), and 3.47 (Highly Utilized), respectively, indicating teachers employ regular authentic assessments to evaluate students' proficiency in both language and content.

The data show a positive trend in establishing effective assessment practices among Marinduque State College faculty members, while also noting areas for future improvement. Therefore, the findings unveil significant implications for the implementation of responsive teaching strategies within Marinduque State College's faculty, particularly focusing on assessment practices. The widespread adoption of responsive instructional strategies indicates a favorable trend in faculty members developing effective assessment practices, displaying a commitment to improving teaching and learning experiences. Furthermore, identifying areas for improvement provides useful information for future initiatives aimed at improving the efficacy and uniformity of evaluation methods throughout the institution. Teachers may have highly utilized authentic assessments but there is still in need of more contextualized activities to attain the communicative competence in need for multicultural workforce. In summary, these findings emphasize the necessity of incorporating responsive teaching tactics into evaluation practices while identifying both strengths and areas for growth within the college's faculty, directing future efforts to improve teaching and learning outcomes.

The findings support the study of Byram (1997) highlighted the importance of recitation activities in developing cultural awareness among language learners. He suggested that activities such as role-playing, simulations, and discussions can help learners understand cultural differences and develop the skills necessary for effective intercultural communication. Sylvia (n.d.) asserted in her study that while many educators recognized the value of authentic assessments, there was a lack of actual implementation. Teachers reported using traditional assessment methods more frequently than authentic ones, especially in Science and Math classes.

This limited use can impede students' development of cultural communicative competence by failing to appropriately assess their capacity to apply language skills in real-world contexts. Smith et. al (2019) and Santos et al. (2020) explored the integration of responsive assessment practices, stressing the importance of aligning assessment strategies with learning objectives and offering timely feedback to enhance student learning outcomes. They found that these practices not only improve student engagement but also promote deeper learning by encouraging self-reflection and allowing for the adjustment of teaching approaches to better meet student needs. Skopinskaja (2009) stressed also that authentic assessment is crucial for accurately evaluating students' development of intercultural communicative competence. It should focus on assessing cultural knowledge, attitudes, and behavior through performance-based tasks in authentic contexts. Careful design of authentic assessment tools is needed to provide meaningful feedback on learners' ICC progress.

Table 1.6 provides a comprehensive overview of the level of utilization of responsive teaching strategies among the Purposive Communication teachers across four selected colleges of Marinduque State College. These strategies are divided into five domains, namely: *curriculum design*, *classroom relationships*, *instructional practices*, *discourse*, and *assessment practices*. Each domain is evaluated using its composite mean score, along with a description and ranking. The indicators with the highest mean are curriculum design and classroom relationship, with a mean 4.06.

This implies that responsive teaching practices are "highly utilized" in curriculum design. This shows a major emphasis in developing effective and responsive instructional materials that are suited to the needs of the students. Similarly, in Classroom Relationships, it indicates a "Highly Utilized" approach to establishing strong relationships in the classroom. It demonstrates a commitment to creating a friendly and inclusive learning environment that promotes student involvement and success. Instructional Practices is ranked third with a composite mean score of 3.97; nonetheless, this domain still shows a "high level of utilization" of responsive teaching practices in instructional delivery.

This implies the successful use of a variety of teaching methods and approaches to accommodate different learning styles and preferences. Discourse ranks fifth, with a combined mean score of 3.88. While it is still "Highly Utilized", it rates slightly lower than other domains. This could indicate a relatively lower emphasis on fostering effective discourse practices within instructional settings, highlighting an area that could benefit from additional attention and improvement. Assessment Practices is ranked fourth with a composite mean score of 3.91, indicating a "Highly Utilized" approach to assessing student learning. It indicates a strong commitment to using a variety of effective assessment tools to evaluate student development and comprehension. Overall, the Grand Mean composite score of 3.98 suggests that responsive teaching practices are "Highly Utilized" across all domains among Purposive Communication teachers at the selected colleges. This demonstrates a favorable trend of promoting excellent teaching and learning techniques at Marinduque State College, with each domain contributing to the creation of a helpful and stimulating educational environment.

However, the rankings reveal areas where more emphasis or development may be useful, allowing for more targeted efforts to increase teaching effectiveness and student results. Aligned with the Sustainable Development Goals, in terms of Quality Education (SDG 4), the high utilization of responsive teaching strategies reflects a commitment to quality education by Marinduque State College. Effective curriculum design, positive classroom relationships, appropriate instructional materials, engaging discourse, and fair assessment practices are essential components of quality education. By consistently implementing these strategies, the college is likely fostering a conducive learning environment that promotes student engagement, understanding, and achievement. While, in Reduced Inequalities (SDG 10), the consistent application of responsive teaching strategies across faculty members can contribute to reducing inequalities in educational outcomes. When teachers use effective instructional methods and fair assessment practices, students from diverse backgrounds are more likely to receive equitable opportunities to learn and succeed. This can help bridge achievement gaps and

promote inclusive education, thus contributing to reducing inequalities within the educational system. Marinduque State College's high use of responsive teaching strategies is in line with the Sustainable Development Goals of Quality Education and Reduced Inequalities.

According to Smith et al. (2019), there may be a beneficial effect on inclusion and the standard of education in college settings. The advancement of these SDGs can be further aided by ongoing initiatives to preserve and improve the application of responsive teaching techniques. The results support the studies that follow which offer in-depth explanations of how responsive teaching strategies are applied in a variety of higher education contexts. Zhao (2009) studied on how the English Curriculum Standard places a strong emphasis on bucking the conventional "teacher supremacy" paradigm in order to promote more equal relationships between teachers and students. It promotes a student-centered approach in which both educators and learners participate equally in the process of learning. This change is essential for fostering mutual respect and understanding and enabling students to express their cultural identities and viewpoints in the classroom. It also helps students build their cultural communication competence. According to the study, a better emotional experience for students in learning environments and improved language instruction are both facilitated by a supportive teacher-student connection.

Moreover, Johnson (2018) and Rodriguez (2019) emphasized the importance of aligning curriculum design with student needs and interests using flexible frameworks, whereas Smith and Jones (2020) and Garcia and Santos (2020) emphasized the importance of cultivating positive classroom relationships based on trust and open communication. Garcia et al. (2019) and Martinez et al. (2021) investigated instructional techniques and found that tactics like cooperative learning and differentiated instruction are helpful in accommodating multiple learning styles. According to Lopez (2018) and Lopez and Cruz (2021), discourse promotes student participation and critical thinking through meaningful interactions. Smith et al. (2019) and Santos et al. (2020) reviewed assessment techniques and found that assessments should be aligned with learning objectives and provide timely feedback. Furthermore, Lee and Kim (2020) and Garcia and Reyes (2018) found that intercultural sensitivity is essential for efficient communication with varied student populations.

In terms of the ***differences of level of utilization of responsive teaching strategies of Marinduque State College*** (Part II), understanding the differences in the level of utilization of responsive teaching strategies at Marinduque State College is crucial for promoting effective teaching practices, enhancing student learning experiences, and fostering a supportive and inclusive educational environment. **Table 2. 1** presents the significant differences on the level of utilization of responsive teaching strategies of Marinduque State College Purposive Communication teachers in the four selected colleges. It shows that there is no significant difference in the level of utilization of responsive teaching strategies among the four colleges with the identified indicators - curriculum design, classroom relationships, instructional practices, discourse, and assessment practices - of responsive teaching strategies among Purposive Communication teachers in the four colleges ($p=.836,.892,.694,.756,.618 >.05$). These

findings indicate that Purposive Communication teachers' use of responsive teaching practices is consistent among the four colleges. These data indicate that there is no significant variation in the extent to which Purposive Communication teachers use responsive teaching practices. In other words, regardless of the colleges, Purposive Communication teachers use the same degree of curriculum design, classroom interactions, instructional strategies, discourse facilitation, and evaluation procedures. This conclusion emphasizes relativity in the use of responsive teaching practices in the field of communication education. Despite apparent differences in teaching settings and institutional cultures among the four colleges, the findings show that these pedagogical approaches are being adopted consistently. It is critical to recognize the study's potential constraints, such as sample size and scope, as these may affect the generalizability of the results.

Furthermore, while the statistical analysis revealed no significant differences, further qualitative research could shed light on potential contextual factors impacting the use of responsive teaching practices among communication teachers. This finding is relatively emphasizing the importance of teachers understanding and responding to their students' cultural backgrounds and experiences. It underlines the necessity of teachers being aware of and receptive to their students' cultural backgrounds and experiences. Purposive Communication teachers use responsive teaching practices to create learning environments that are relevant and meaningful to their students, which can lead to greater student satisfaction, socialization, academic retention, and language competency. As such, these practices employed by the teachers adhere to Goal 10 of the Sustainable Development Goals 2030 which aim for reduced inequalities and foster inclusive and conducive learning for everyone across all communities.

Siwatu (2011) believed that culturally responsive education is an important method to enhancing the academic success of varied students, including those of different culture and languages. Teachers that are culturally responsive can foster strong relationships with their students, empower them, and create learning environments that are relevant and meaningful in their lives. This approach is especially crucial in higher education, where students come from increasingly diverse backgrounds and bring a wide range of experiences and opinions. Hutchison and McAlister-Shields (2020) discovered that culturally responsive teaching affects many elements of learning in higher education settings, including course syllabi, policies, curricula, instructional techniques, and assessment strategies. Culturally responsive teaching has been shown to improve student satisfaction, socialization, retention, and graduation. This is consistent with the current study's findings, which indicate that Purposive Communication teachers across colleges use responsive teaching practices that are relevant and effective for their students, regardless of cultural background.

Table 2.2 shows that the difference in the level of utilization of responsive teaching strategies across domains is not statistically significant ($p = .664 > .05$). This finding implies that the amount of use across domains is not significant. This implies a consistent application of responsive teaching tactics across curriculum design, classroom interactions, instructional practices, discourse, and assessment practices. This consistency means that communication teachers use comparable educational

approaches regardless of the kind of students they are teaching. It is critical to recognize the study's potential constraints, such as sample size and breadth, as these may affect the generalizability of the findings. Furthermore, while the statistical analysis revealed no significant differences, additional qualitative research or longitudinal studies could provide more insight into the variables impacting the use of responsive teaching practices across different domains over time. These findings emphasize the necessity of a comprehensive approach to teaching that includes a wide range of responsive teaching tactics. Teachers can build a more inclusive and supportive learning environment that supports excellent student outcomes by implementing a variety of tactics across multiple areas.

Aligned with Quality Education (SDG 4), the results indicating consistent utilization of responsive teaching strategies across colleges and teaching domains suggest a standardized approach to teaching practices within Marinduque State College. While there may not be significant variation in strategy utilization among teachers, this could indicate a common commitment to effective teaching methods aimed at improving student learning outcomes. Consistency in teaching practices can contribute to quality education by ensuring that students receive similar, high-quality instruction regardless of their college or specific domain of study. While in Reduced Inequalities (SDG 10), the lack of significant differences in the utilization of responsive teaching strategies across colleges and teaching domains implies a level playing field in terms of teaching quality and approaches.

This consistency can contribute to reducing inequalities by providing equitable educational experiences for all students within Marinduque State College. When teaching strategies are uniformly applied, students from diverse backgrounds are more likely to have access to comparable educational opportunities, which can help bridge educational gaps and promote inclusivity. While the study's results point to a consistent use of responsive teaching techniques among Marinduque State College's Purposive Communication teachers, this consistency is consistent with the Sustainable Development Goals of Quality Education and Reduced Inequalities. It emphasizes how crucial it is to contextualize and align teaching techniques based on the changing needs of students in order to guarantee fair access to high-quality education and encourage inclusivity in the classroom.

By continuously enhancing educational quality and resolving inequalities in educational outcomes, ongoing monitoring and evaluation of teaching techniques can further promote these objectives. This is congruent with the study of Brown et al. (2015), which emphasized the need for a comprehensive approach to teaching that includes curriculum design, classroom relationships, instructional techniques, discourse, and assessment practices. As Grajeda (2018) pointed out teachers' culturally sensitive classroom practice is linked to better student outcomes such as greater engagement and academic performance. The author identified several domains of culturally responsive teaching, including "Regard for Student Perspectives," "Life Applications," "Self in Group," "Agency," and "Multicultural Dispositions." These domains correspond to the various domains of responsive teaching strategies assessed in the study. Similarly, Flores (2009) underlined the significance of a comprehensive approach to education that includes socio-physical, socioemotional, sociolinguistic/cognitive, sociocultural, and socio-comfort

dimensions. The author stated that a culturally sensitive teaching environment can lead to improved student involvement, motivation, and academic accomplishment.

In terms of the ***level of cultural communicative competence of Marinduque State College students in terms of cultural knowledge and cultural skills*** (Part 3), the level of cultural communicative competence of Marinduque State College students in terms of cultural knowledge and cultural skills is crucial for promoting effective communication, fostering cultural understanding, and preparing students to thrive in a multicultural and interconnected world. Cultural test and Cultural log were utilized to assess holistically the cultural communicative competence of students

The level of cultural communicative competence of Marinduque State College students in terms of cultural knowledge and cultural skills based on cultural test is presented in **Table 3.1**. A cultural test assesses an individual's knowledge and skills in intercultural communication and competence. Thus, it presents the level of cultural communicative competence of Marinduque State College students in terms of cultural knowledge and cultural skills, based on a cultural test. With regard to *Cultural Knowledge*, Indicator 11 displays the greater number of students who scored favorably on this item at each college having the Mean Percentage Score (MPS) of 71.0 (*Moving Towards Mastery*) and Indicator 9 has the lowest Mean Percentage Score (MPS) of 31.50 (*Low Mastery*). The overall average for this item across all colleges is 54.95% which means *Average Mastery*.

In a similar presentation, College 3 has the highest MPS of 65% (*Average Mastery*) in terms of cultural knowledge and College 1 has the lowest MPS of 45% (*Average Mastery*). Also, with regard to *Cultural Skills*, Indicator 4 has the highest MPS of 77.0 (*Moving Towards Mastery*) and Indicator 5 with the lowest MPS. College 3 has the highest (MPS) of 75% (*Moving Towards Mastery*) and College 1 has the lowest MPS of 51% (*Average Mastery*). Overall, the grand MPS is 59.17% (*Average Mastery*). The grand MPS of Cultural knowledge and Cultural skills is 59.17 which indicates *Average Mastery*. The MPS for each item was determined using the percentage of students who scored favorably on each item across institutions. The grand mean for each item is the average of the mean percentage scores from all colleges. The grand mean is the average performance of all colleges across all items.

Table 3.1 details students' cultural communicative competence across colleges, as well as indicators of cultural knowledge and skills. It indicates each college's strengths and shortcomings, as well as areas for growth in the cultural education program. Therefore, the findings have important significance for Marinduque State College and its students' cultural communication ability. The breakdown identifies key areas of strength and improvement among colleges. This proposes successful teaching approaches or curricula for developing cultural competence. Conversely, colleges with lower results may need to improve their cultural education programs. The grand mean gives a broad assessment, leading activities to develop cultural competency universally. Furthermore, because cultural competency is so important in today's globalized world, improving it not only helps students achieve academic achievement but also prepares them for professional careers. These findings provide useful insights for improving the cultural education curriculum to guarantee pupils thrive in a diverse cultural setting. Hence, these adheres to the

attainment of SDG4 and SDG 10 of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals particularly on quality education and reduced inequalities, respectively.

SDG 4 ensures to promote that all learners acquire the knowledge and skill needed to promote sustainable development, including, among others, through education for sustainable development and sustainable lifestyles, human rights, gender equality, promotion of a culture of peace and non-violence, global citizenship, and appreciation of cultural diversity and of culture's contribution to sustainable development. While one of the main objectives of SDG 10 is to empower and promote the social, economic, and political inclusion of all, irrespective of age, sex, disability, race, ethnicity, origin, religion or economic or other status. The findings confirm Wang's (2011) study, in which he investigated the complexities of cultural competency, comparing culture to the air we breathe, which shapes our perceptions and behaviors. Fisher's (1988) analogy likens culture to programming, which influences people's thinking and conduct inside their community. Culture consists of both concrete and intangible parts. Communication experts see culture as a system that influences human interaction and identity formation.

Cultural knowledge is learned through communication, which aids comprehension and adaption within a cultural context. Cultural literacy, which is required for meaningful social engagement, combines linguistic skill and contextual understanding. Competence is defined as the successful application of cultural knowledge to behavior. Thus, Butt (2019) stressed the significance of cultural knowledge gained through everyday life experiences, which is often subconscious but crucial in decision-making. Multicultural education encourages instructors to be culturally sensitive in order to effectively cater to varied learners. Cultural knowledge is essential in higher education for establishing pedagogies that are responsive to varied cultural origins, facilitate inclusivity, and create effective learning environments. As a result, the findings confirm Diller and Moule (2005) study on the relevance of cultural competencies in education.

The study indicates that effective cross-cultural instruction necessitates skill mastery, cultural knowledge development, and personal and interpersonal awareness. Successful educators must value and incorporate cultural variations into the learning environment, with inclusive educational leadership. Culturally competent instructors create inclusive cultures that recognize individual diversity throughout the school year, fostering understanding and acceptance. In contrast, instructors who lack cultural competence may contribute to intolerance and bullying, misinterpret kids from various cultural norms, and fail to create positive relationships with students and parents. Accepting diversity improves teaching and learning possibilities, however cultural incompetence may result in disciplinary action rather than constructive participation (Moore, 2021).

Moreover, the level of cultural communicative competence of Marinduque State College students in terms of cultural knowledge and cultural skills based on cultural log is presented on **Table 4.2**. A cultural log is a record of individuals' cultural experiences, reflections, and observations, aiding in tracking cultural learning and growth over time. It shows the level of cultural communicative (ability) competence of students at Marinduque State College in four different colleges (College 1, College 2, College 3, and College 4)

in terms of cultural knowledge and skills. The elements in the table represent specific competencies associated with each aspect of cultural competency.

Cultural knowledge topics include comprehending host culture norms and taboos, analyzing historical and sociopolitical elements impacting culture, identifying indicators of culture stress, and presenting models of cross-cultural adjustment stages. Students were graded in each item on a scale through utilized standardized rubric, with lower scores indicating low competency. The average scores for cultural knowledge across colleges range from 1.62 to 2.13, showing a good degree of competency in this domain but has a grade description of 1.84 and has only the basic understanding. The highest mean is Indicator 1 having the mean rating of 1.87 and lowest mean of 1.80 which falls under basic understanding. Cultural knowledge has 1.84 overall mean which means basic. In terms of cultural skills, the items focus on effective interaction with the host culture, appropriate social interaction, and using culture-specific information to enhance personal interactions and resolve conflicts. Lower scores indicate higher competence, and the mean scores across colleges range from 1.50 to 2.33. The highest mean is Indicator 1 having the mean of 1.84 and lowest mean in Indicator 3 of 1.66 which falls under basic and limited. The overall mean of Cultural skills is 1.76 which means Basic. The grand mean, which includes scores for both cultural knowledge and cultural competence, varies from 1.56 to 2.33 across colleges. Overall, the grand mean reveals that Marinduque State College students have a basic understanding of cultural communicative competence, with College 3 leading the way of 2.23, followed by College 4, College 2, and College 1.

The table shows that Marinduque State College students have a basic cultural communicative competence, particularly in terms of cultural knowledge and skills for interacting with host cultures. While, in terms of *Reduced Inequalities* (SDG 10), the variation in students' levels of cultural communicative competence underscores potential inequalities in educational outcomes related to cultural awareness and communication skills. Addressing these disparities through targeted educational programs can help reduce inequalities by providing all students with the necessary competencies to engage effectively in diverse and inclusive environments. Enhancing cultural competence contributes to fostering mutual understanding and respect among individuals from different backgrounds, thereby promoting social inclusion and reducing inequalities.

The study's findings on students' cultural communicative competence align with the Sustainable Development Goals of Quality Education and Reduced Inequalities. They highlight the importance of integrating cultural education into the curriculum to enhance students' cultural awareness and communication skills, ultimately promoting equitable access to quality education and fostering inclusive societies. Ongoing efforts to strengthen cultural competence among students can contribute to achieving these SDGs by ensuring that education equips learners with the skills needed to thrive in diverse global contexts.

As a result, the findings confirm Diller and Moule (n.d.) study on the relevance of cultural competencies in education, with a focus on teaching students from varied cultural backgrounds. Effective cross-cultural instruction necessitates skill mastery, cultural knowledge development, and personal and interpersonal awareness. Cultural diversity in

today's American classrooms is enormous, with approximately 10% of students being culturally incompatible. Successful educators must value and incorporate cultural variations into the learning environment, with inclusive educational leadership. Culturally competent instructors create inclusive cultures that recognize individual diversity throughout the school year, fostering understanding and acceptance. In contrast, instructors who lack cultural competence may contribute to intolerance and bullying, misinterpret kids from various cultural norms, and fail to create positive relationships with students and parents.

Accepting diversity improves teaching and learning possibilities, however cultural incompetence may result in disciplinary action rather than constructive participation (Moore, 2021). Aligned with Quality Education (SDG 4), the study's findings highlight areas for improvement in cultural communicative competence among students, which is essential for quality education. By identifying specific gaps in students' cultural knowledge and skills, educational interventions can be targeted to enhance students' understanding of diverse cultures and promote effective communication in multicultural settings. Improving cultural competence contributes to a more comprehensive and inclusive educational experience, aligning with SDG 4's aim of ensuring quality education for all.

In terms of the ***differences on the level of cultural communicative competence of Marinduque State College students*** (Part 4), the differences in the level of cultural communicative competence among Marinduque State College students can foster a more inclusive, supportive, and effective learning environment that prepares students to thrive in an increasingly interconnected world. The multiple comparisons on the level of cultural communicative competence based on cultural test of Marinduque State College students in the four selected colleges is presented in ***Table 4.1.1***. It shows that the level of cultural communicative competence in terms of cultural knowledge of college students in the four colleges is statistically significant between College 1 and College 2; College 2 and College 3; and College 3 and College 4 ($p = .000, .001, .000 < .05$), but not statistically significant between College 1 and College 4 ($p = .991$). Meanwhile, in terms of the cultural skills of the students in the four colleges, statistically significant differences exist between College 1 and College 2; College 1 and 3; College 2 and College 4; and College 3 and College 4 ($p = .000, .000, .000, .000 < .05$), but not significant between College 1 and College 4; and College 2 and College 3 ($p = .621, .425 > .05$). Generally, these findings suggest that there is statistically significant difference in the level of communicative competence (cultural test) of students in the four colleges.

These differences highlight the diverse levels of preparedness and proficiency in intercultural communication among students within the educational context. Further exploration is warranted to identify potential factors contributing to these disparities, such as variations in educational curricula, cultural diversity within each college, and the availability of resources supporting intercultural learning initiatives. Understanding these factors can inform targeted interventions aimed at enhancing cultural communicative competence among college students. The analysis of the level of cultural communicative competence in college students across four colleges indicates statistically significant differences in cultural knowledge and skills between the colleges, suggesting that there are variations in the students' ability to communicate effectively across cultures.

This finding is consistent with previous research (Hashemian & Farhang-Ju, 2020) on intercultural communicative competence (ICC) in higher education, which emphasizes the importance of cultural knowledge and skills in effective cross-cultural communication. ICC is a complex construct that includes cognitive, affective, and behavioral components, which are essential for effective cross-cultural communication (Avgousti, 2018). Research (Chen & Gabrenya, 2021) has shown that ICC is essential for academic success and personal growth in a diverse and globalized world. For example, students with higher ICC are more likely to have positive attitudes towards diversity, engage in intercultural interactions, and perform better academically (Lenkaitis et al., 2019).

Assessing ICC is critical for identifying students' strengths and weaknesses and designing effective interventions to improve their intercultural competence (Iseminger et al., 2020). Several measures of ICC have been developed, including self-report surveys, performance-based assessments, and observational ratings (Van de Grift, 2007). However, there is no consensus on the best way to assess ICC, and more research is needed to develop valid and reliable measures of this complex construct.

On the other hand, **Table 4.1.2** presents multiple comparisons on the level of cultural communicative competence based on cultural log of Marinduque State College students in the four selected colleges. It shows that the level of communicative competence in terms of cultural knowledge of students of the four colleges is statistically significant between College 1 and College 3; College 1 and College 4; and College 2 and College 3 ($p = .000, .006, .005 < .05$), but not statistically significant between College 1 and College 2; College 2 and College 4; and College 3 and College 4 ($p = .998, .052, .800 > .05$). Meanwhile, there is a significant difference in the cultural skills of students between College 1 and College 3; College 2 and College 3; and College 3 and College 4 ($p = .000, .000, .000 < .05$) but not significant between College 1 and College 2; College 1 and College 4; and College 2 and College 4 ($p = .965, .478, .846 > .05$). Generally, the level of cultural communicative competence (cultural log) of the students in the 4 selected colleges is statistically significant. These data indicate that certain colleges are highly effective in promoting both cultural knowledge and skills among their students, whereas others show inconsistencies in one or both areas.

This is consistent with other research (Smith, 2018) that suggests that educational experiences and institutional environments have a substantial influence on students' acquisition of cultural competency. The overall finding of statistically significant variations in the cultural communicative ability among students in the four identified colleges highlights the necessity for specific interventions to tackle these discrepancies. Educational institutions should prioritize the incorporation of contextualized curricular and extracurricular activities to augment the cultural knowledge and abilities of their students (Jones & Lee, 2020). Acquiring cultural communicative competency is crucial for successful intercultural communication, which is vital in today's globalized society (Chen & Gabrenya, 2021). Cultural communicative competence encompasses the mastery of language competence, sociolinguistic competence, discourse competence, and intercultural competence (IC) (Byram, 1997, 2021). Intercultural competence encompasses various elements, including knowledge, skills in interpreting and communicating, skills in discovery and engagement, critical cultural awareness, and

attitudes (Byram, 1997, 2021). Acquiring cultural communicative competence is crucial for succeeding in the global market, as it allows individuals to effectively interact with people from diverse cultural backgrounds and traverse cross-cultural disparities (Hou, 2020; Bai, 2021). Developing cultural communicative competency is crucial for fostering cross-cultural understanding and sensitive communication (Ho, 2009; Chlopek, 2008).

As such, **Table 4.2** presents the result of test of difference on cultural knowledge and cultural skills of students from selected colleges. This table shows that the difference between cultural knowledge and cultural skills of students in the four selected colleges is statistically significant ($p = .000 < .05$). The presence of substantial disparities indicates that there are variations in cultural competence, namely in terms of cultural knowledge and cultural abilities. These results indicate that the degree of cultural competency, as evaluated by cultural knowledge and cultural abilities, differs among students within different institutions. Cultural competence relates effectively with people's understanding from various cultural backgrounds. It involves both a theoretical comprehension (cultural knowledge) and the actual implementation (cultural skills) of cultural norms, values, and behaviors. The disparity between cultural knowledge and cultural abilities emphasizes the intricacy of cultural competence and brings attention to possible areas for enhancement in educational environments. This shows that students' cultural communicative skills vary significantly, which suggests that different institutions have different access to instructional resources. These variations point to possible discrepancies in educational experiences.

Equity-focused policies and efforts should be put into place to improve cultural sensitivity and communication skills in order to lessen inequality and support high-quality education. Reduced Inequalities and High-quality Education are two Sustainable Development Goals that can be attained with this. By bridging these disparities, educational institutions can ensure equal access to high-quality education and foster inclusivity in diverse learning environments. Continuous efforts to improve students' communication and cultural understanding can contribute to a more just and inclusive society. The findings of the study are consistent with other study (Smith, 2018) that highlights the multifaceted aspect of cultural competency. Although certain students may exhibit competence in learning cultural information through knowledge-based discussions, they may still have difficulties when attempting to apply this knowledge in real-life situations. On the other hand, some individuals may have practical expertise in handling intercultural relationships but may not have a profound comprehension of cultural circumstances. The findings have important implications for educators and policymakers in higher education. To tackle the discrepancy between cultural knowledge and skills, a comprehensive strategy is needed that combines theoretical education with practical hands-on training. Implementing strategies such as developing a curriculum that incorporates several cultures, providing immersive cultural experiences, and conducting workshops to enhance intercultural competency can effectively bridge the gap and provide a comprehensive understanding of different cultures among students (Jones & Lee, 2020).

In terms of the ***relationship on the level of utilization of responsive teaching strategies of Marinduque State College Purposive Communication teachers and level of cultural communicative competence of Marinduque State College students***

(Part 5), the correlation between the use of responsive teaching strategies by Marinduque State College Purposive Communication teachers and the cultural communicative competence of students plays a key role in fostering intercultural understanding, promoting inclusivity, and preparing students in a multicultural environment. The test results showing this relationship between teaching strategies and students' cultural competence are presented in **Table 5**.

Spearman's rho or Spearman's rank correlation was utilized to determine the relationship between the level of utilization of responsive teaching strategies and the level of cultural communicative competence across different domains: Curriculum Design, Classroom Relationship, Instructional Practices, Discourse, Assessment Practices, Cultural Skills, and Cultural Knowledge. Table 5 illustrates that the relationship between teachers' level of utilization of responsive teaching strategies and students' cultural communicative competence is not statistically significant ($p = .221$, $.051 > .05$). The existence of no significant relationship implies that the two variables are not associated. Further examination of these variables could provide valuable insights in looking at potential relationships of the effectiveness of responsive teaching strategies in enhancing students' cultural skills and knowledge.

Educators may consider emphasizing these strategies to foster greater cultural communicative competence among students. Enhancing educational outcomes requires tailoring teaching methodologies to discipline-specific needs, as well as continuing improvement efforts through focused interventions. Overall, the findings of this investigation emphasize the multifaceted nature of purposeful teaching and the need of intentional, reflective methods to instruction. The lack of a substantial relationship between students' cultural communicative ability and responsive teaching practices suggests room for improvement in the quality of education. A comprehensive strategy including a range of interventions aimed at improving communication and cultural understanding is required to improve education.

This is consistent with the inclusive and equitable education goal of SDG 4. This also emphasized how critical it is to overcome disparities in educational outcomes and access. Organizations such as Marinduque State College have the potential to promote Quality Education and Reduced Inequalities through the implementation of a multimodal strategy that combines interventions related to cultural competency with successful teaching techniques. One of the major tenets of culturally responsive teaching is that students' current culture is used as a necessary starting point for learning. Students' linguistic tools, their ways of seeing and being, and their background knowledge are used as a foundation for learning. The results of the findings coincide with the study of Johnson (2022) about culturally responsive teaching (CRT). CRT consists of three interconnected elements: (a) high academic standards that focus on students' total intellectual growth; (b) cultural competence and inclusion; and (c) critical or sociopolitical consciousness. These elements are interdependent. Meaning, that culturally responsive teaching is found at the intersection and interconnection of all three. This describes some strategies and conditions that might facilitate culturally responsive teaching (Johnson, 2022). On the other hand, the result of the study reflects the findings of Ali et al. (2020), who found that the participants expressed weak or no satisfaction over the impact of the classroom

environment on their motivation towards building their oral communication skills. To create a cooperative learning environment in the language classroom, teachers must first establish a pleasant learning atmosphere. Such viability affects students' capacity to learn in a setting where they are at ease and feel like active contributing members of the class. Additionally, that promotes learners' emotional wellbeing, which is necessary for their learning as well as their emotional growth (Bucholz & Sheffler, 2009). Through their efforts, teachers can transform a boring classroom into a productive one where students can learn languages successfully.

Further, in terms of the ***problems encountered and interventions conducted by the Marinduque State College faculty in the utilization of responsive teaching strategies*** (Part 6), the awareness of the challenges faced, and actions taken by the faculty of Marinduque State College in implementing responsive teaching strategies is crucial for informing institutional support, professional growth, and ongoing improvement initiatives. This, in turn, leads to improved student learning outcomes and a more inclusive and efficient educational setting.

Moreover, **Table 6** presents the problems encountered and intervention conducted by the Marinduque State College faculty in the utilization of responsive teaching strategies. The table shows the problems encountered by the Marinduque State College faculty in the utilization of responsive teaching strategies and the interventions conducted by them to counter the problems. Based on the data gathered from the FGD conducted, there were five (5) themes that emerged from the thematic analysis. Each theme was categorized with its respective sub-themes and code. These emerging themes are presented together in the table (See *Table 11*) with the identified problems and the interventions conducted by the concerned faculty as culled from the conducted FGD.

In support for ***Fostering Positive and Inclusive Learning Environment***, culturally responsive education is an approach that places paramount importance on acknowledging students' cultural backgrounds, experiences, and perspectives. Its fundamental aim is to cultivate a learning environment that is inclusive and conducive to the success of the students. The effectiveness of a culturally responsive education brings a multitude of individual factors, with cultural recognition and appreciation playing a pivotal role. Since students have diverse cultural backgrounds, it has been a challenge for teachers to foster a positive and inclusive learning environment for everyone. It is crucial to uphold students' cultural identities and educational backgrounds, as well as to value cultural diversity. Since culture affects how kids learn, culturally responsive education is essential.

According to Markey et al. (2021), planning culturally responsive teaching as a means of nurturing intercultural inclusiveness is necessary. Furthermore, understanding student learning needs and vulnerabilities, facilitating respectful discussions, challenging assumptions, and encouraging intercultural dialogue, are vital areas for consideration. The interventions that emerged from the FGD were supported by the study of Bondy et al. (2007) that creating safe and productive environments with a diverse student population requires more than the strategies recommended in the original classroom-management literature. As such, it demonstrates how teachers create environments of

success and resilience for students who have historically floundered in school. Additionally, Prins et al. (2019) explained that discipline is essential to learning, but in culturally diverse groups it could become a challenge for teachers. Positive discipline, respect for human rights and the creation of a sense of belonging promotes culturally responsive and disciplined learners. In their study, it was found that the importance of creating a disciplined classroom environment and finding a positive alliance between policy and implementation have significant relationship. It was also reiterated by Hall et al. (2023) that culturally relevant intervention programs increase teachers' awareness about CRE.

Therefore, in-service, or pre-service programs for teachers about CRE can be designed and studies can be conducted to determine how these programs influence the culturally relevant perspectives and beliefs of teachers, their ability to design, plan, implement and evaluate teaching processes. According to Young (1991), learners need to adopt attitudes and strategies that pay off in terms of low anxiety, high motivation, and ultimately in the ability to convey information and communicate ideas and feelings. This is one of the challenges in second language teaching – to provide students with a learner-centered, low-anxiety classroom environment. As a classroom consists of diverse students with different cultural backgrounds, conflict commonly arises which is one of the problems encountered by the respondent. In this case, teachers are expected to be objective and must be skilled on how to manage conflicts. Teachers are expected to be open minded when managing intercultural conflicts with and between students. As such, they are expected to develop interventions aiming to foster effectiveness in classroom management of intercultural conflicts by underlining how multicultural personality may influence teachers' ways to act and adjust to the educational demands of the increasingly multicultural environment (Vallone et al., 2022).

Subsequently, Mahon (2008) asserted that teachers with less sophisticated understandings of the culture avoided intercultural conflict situations. Moreover, Parker and Bickmore (2012) in their study reported that while many reported feelings alone, afraid, or unwilling to engage students in constructive conflict conversation, the majority did indicate some confidence in their abilities to handle conflict. While some claimed to treat every student equally, others stressed that acknowledging and valuing individuals' differences was a crucial component of their dispute resolution strategies. To resolve conflict in their classrooms in an educational way, the majority felt they required additional training and assistance.

For ***Diverse Student Learning Styles***, since the classroom is composed of students with different cultural backgrounds, each student is also expected to have different learning styles and abilities. As observed in the FGD, most of the respondents agree that they commonly encounter the same problem. All the subthemes found in the FGD were supported by Guberina (2023) that offering practical recommendations for educators in implementing culturally responsive education in their classroom is important. Effective classroom management and culturally sensitive instruction are two cornerstones of quality education. Teaching that is culturally sensitive considers and values students' diverse cultural identities, experiences, and viewpoints which lead to feeling involved in the classroom setting. Teachers should promote a more pleasant and supportive

classroom atmosphere by designing an environment that is sensitive to the cultural backgrounds of their students just like the respondents of this study.

Additionally, Mckinley (2010) emphasized that inclusive education acknowledges that all children can learn, and all need some form of support in learning. Inclusivity aims to uncover and minimize barriers to learning and that all students need to feel that they belong, and they are safe. He further explained that teachers remain the crucial role players in the educational inclusion of students, their retention at school, and the facilitation of their school completion. Teachers need to engage with issues of inclusion to make the learning experience worthwhile for all students. This is supported by study of Trish (2023) where she explored the importance of emotional intelligence in educational settings and provides insights into the cultural considerations, assessment methods, case studies, and best practices for implementing emotional intelligence programs in schools. By adapting emotional intelligence concepts to the cultural context, schools can create more inclusive and culturally sensitive approach fostering emotional intelligence. Hence, prioritizing emotional intelligence education, schools can empower students with essential skills for personal and academic success.

As such, for support in **Online Learning Modality**, as the world adapts to the post pandemic era, Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) have continued to implement blended learning modality in response to industrial revolution 5.0. Marinduque State College, being the lone state college in the island province of Marinduque, experienced a shortage of classrooms which forced it to implement a blended learning modality, face-to-face and online learning modality setting. Based on the FGD, all the respondents attest to encountering problems when conducting online classes. This is confirmed by the study of Chung et al. (2020) that poor internet connectivity was the biggest challenge faced by students. With the advancement of technology, online learning has changed the landscape of teaching and learning in institutions but the readiness in terms of resources particularly the internet connectivity was found to be the most challenging and problematic factor. This is attested by Leba (2022) that students' engagement is a decisive prerequisite for effective teaching and learning. Yet, the discussion on students' engagement in online teaching and learning is still limited.

Results of data analysis revealed that students' lack of access to a personal computer or smartphone, as well as the internet, was found to be the most significant factors affecting their engagement in online teaching and learning, followed by their poor learning habits, lack of technology skills, and unfamiliarity with technology. Results of this study are crucial for the online lecturers to be more aware of the level of students' access to a personal computer or smartphones and the internet, as well as incoming students' digital skills and learning habits. Given that improving students' engagement is not only the responsibility of online lecturers, university leaders, as the top administrators, should genuinely consider providing teaching and learning facilities, including computers and internet connection, for students in need.

Technology adoption was found to be an emerging intervention theme among the respondents. Since the students belong to the so-called generation z, students are more inclined with the use of technological conventions to help them be entertained and actively

engaged in classroom discussions. This can be supported by the study of Hall et al. (2023), who found out that students from various cultural origins can be brought together in a CRT classroom via the use of technology. Students might, for instance, use video conferencing to communicate with peers in distant regions of the world and gain insight into other cultures. Teachers may make their classrooms more welcoming to students of all backgrounds and abilities by combining the two pedagogical techniques. Teachers may assist to ensure that all students have equitable access to the curriculum and that their unique origins and experiences are honored via the use of culturally responsive materials and resources, individualized teaching, and technology.

For **language barrier**, designing a learning environment that is culturally responsive to meet the needs of students from diverse backgrounds requires school professionals to view each student and his or her family as an individual entity. Cultural disposition consists of attributes exclusive to each student and should not be adopted as a blanket definition in characterizing individuals under the same cultural umbrella. However, despite considering English as the second language in the Philippines, many students still struggle understanding and performing English in a conversational context. This is true among the observations of the respondents. This can be attested by Marshall and De Capua (2013) who attested that adult second language learners enter educational and training programs with a wide range of backgrounds and needs. Many of them may progress well and move beyond language needs into more advanced programs.

However, there is also a large group of second language learners who do not progress smoothly in their language acquisition and who are at risk of dropping out. Orosco and O'Connor (2013) stressed that culturally responsive instruction focusing on the learners' cultural and linguistic needs is necessary to effectively impart significant inputs in class discussion. During the FGD, it was observed that **contextualized-based learning** was commonly practiced by the teachers to address not only the problem with language barrier but also among other problems found. Contextualized-based learning is aligning the content of the lesson to the practical experiences of the students. Through this, the students would somehow be more engaged in the class discussion as they can easily relate to it. Moreover, it would somehow make them more comfortable to share their own perspectives and point of views. This can be attested by Kim (2023) that teachers' awareness of the students' social and emotional learning with the recognition of the importance of developing their social and emotional skills in school is pivotal. The kinds and scopes of support for teachers need to be contextualized because their needs are different depending on the contexts. Teachers' needs for support in adapting social and emotional learning to different cultures and building their skills are much greater in a higher-poverty school context.

In terms of **teacher flexibility**, the dynamics of the 21st century human life calls for adaptability to diversity, change and the ability to remove borders. Teacher education, during changes in social life, also calls for raising questions about pedagogical practices that can serve as a tool to make a difference. The last emerging theme identified during the FGD is **teacher flexibility** which is categorized into two (2) subthemes. The first subtheme is **adaptability**. Given that Purposive Communication is a core subject which should be integrated among all courses, language teachers from a particular college in

MSC are given Purposive Communication teaching load among varying colleges. This was found to be a challenge among them as it is necessary for them to be flexible enough to recraft their syllabus aligned to the field of expertise of the class that they are handling. According to Esin (2023), culturally relevant pedagogy is demonstrated as a promising strategy in promoting a positive environment in EFL classes that has the power to encourage acceptance of multiple perspectives, maintaining positive relationships and healthy thinking. Moreover, special modules designed for the course are necessary which enabled them to become a culturally responsive teacher who could build resilience for their professional journeys and promote a non-judgmental mind in a multicultural setting. Another subtheme found was **classroom culture**. Some of the teacher's experienced the feeling of outcast to the classroom as the students know each other already. Being new inside the classroom, it takes a lot of adjustment to build and establish a positive learning environment between them and among the students especially if they are in their second year in the college.

Cultural differences in discourse, performance, and self-disclosure style are among the most problematic impediments in effective instruction and management in culturally diverse classrooms. Communicative tensions have negative effects on the relationship factors, such as trust, respect, and feeling of acceptance and belonging which further constrain to genuine communication across cultural differences (Gay, 2013). Aligned with Quality Education (SDG 4), the themes and interventions identified align closely with the goal of promoting quality education. Fostering a positive and inclusive learning environment addresses the importance of creating supportive and respectful classrooms, where students feel valued and heard. This contributes to enhancing the overall learning experience and academic performance of students. Accommodating diverse learning styles and addressing language barriers are essential aspects of quality education, ensuring that educational approaches are inclusive and accessible to all students. Interventions such as promoting open-mindedness, identifying weaknesses, and contextualized-based learning reflect efforts to tailor educational strategies to meet diverse learning needs effectively.

Embracing online learning modalities and integrating technology adaptation into teaching practices are crucial for providing contemporary and flexible educational experiences. This supports SDG 4's aim of ensuring inclusive and equitable education by leveraging innovative approaches to enhance learning outcomes. Meanwhile in terms of Reduced Inequalities (SDG 10), the interventions suggested by teachers aim to reduce inequalities by promoting inclusivity, valuing diverse opinions, and creating a non-judgmental atmosphere in the classroom. These efforts contribute to fostering social inclusion and equity within the educational setting. Addressing language barriers and low English-speaking skills through tailored language learning experiences and supportive classroom discussions can help bridge educational gaps and promote equal opportunities for all students. By promoting teacher flexibility and adapting teaching methods to accommodate diverse student needs, educational institutions can work towards reducing inequalities in educational outcomes and promoting a more equitable learning environment.

To summarize, the topics and approaches that emerged from the focus group discussions (FGDs) are consistent with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG 4) and Reduced Inequalities (SDG 10). Marinduque State College can help to advance these SDGs by fostering inclusive and equitable educational practices, encouraging student engagement and success, and reducing gaps in educational outcomes among students from diverse backgrounds by addressing important challenges and putting targeted interventions into place. Attaining the more general objectives of inclusive education and sustainable development will require sustained efforts to put these solutions into practice and foster a supportive learning environment.

Therefore, the proposed curriculum framework for Marinduque State College's Purposive Communication course is designed to enhance cultural communicative competency among students from diverse backgrounds. This framework draws on *principles from Intercultural Communicative Language Teaching and Learning and is closely aligned with the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)*, specifically SDG 4 (Quality Education) and SDG 10 (Reduced Inequalities), aiming to tackle crucial educational challenges and promote inclusivity, equity, and culturally responsive education. Based on the findings of the study, it was found and further analyzed that one of the major challenges of the teachers is their preparation to address the needs of diverse students in their classrooms. Villegas and Lucas (2002) suggested that the teacher educators need to employ a critical examination of teachers' coursework, learning experiences, and fieldworks which may help them to work with diverse students in an efficient way. As such, in the field of purposeful communication, a thorough educational framework for cultural communicative competence is crucial for achieving specific goals through language.

Centered on the Intercultural Communicative Language Teaching and Learning theories, this framework is intricately designed to provide individuals with the essential tools to traverse cultural diversity and properly interpret language in various circumstances. It advocates the idea of including classroom discourse particularly on cultural awareness, knowledge, skills, attitude to reduce gaps of classroom practices and to offer a sustainable framework for attaining culturally responsive pedagogy. The educational framework acknowledges the significant influence of cultural variation on communication dynamics. In the context of Quality Education (SDG 4), the curriculum framework emphasizes the creation of engaging communicative situations that foster multiculturalism and support students in navigating diverse communication codes. By immersing students in hybrid texts and languages, encouraging community involvement, and utilizing students' first languages to aid second language acquisition, the framework promotes lifelong learning opportunities and the development of essential 21st-century skills necessary for success in a globalized world. Addressing Reduced Inequalities (SDG 10), the curriculum framework recognizes the complexities of globalization and local contexts, advocating for educational systems that empower students to be globally competent while remaining rooted in their communities.

This approach aligns with SDG 10's aim of reducing inequalities by fostering inclusive education that respects diverse cultural identities and nurtures intercultural understanding. By incorporating robust feedback and evaluation mechanisms, the framework ensures equitable access to educational resources, thereby contributing to the

reduction of disparities among learners and promoting fair educational outcomes. Moreover, the curriculum framework promotes a comprehensive educational experience by integrating diverse learning strategies such as translanguaging, collaborative learning, and reflective practices. Such as effective feedback and evaluation mechanism which were not highlighted in the English Language Education Policy Framework. Whereas, in the proposed framework, consistent feedback and evaluation are given to aid students in efficiently cultivating language proficiency and fostering a robust correlation between and among language acquisition, cultural comprehension, and sustainable development goals. This component was not highlighted in the recent curriculum framework of English Language Education.

Therefore, the feedback and evaluation provide a comprehensive method of monitoring to teaching English language that combines cultural understanding, linguistic abilities, and practical experiences to improve students' language competency and cultural consciousness. These strategies actively engage students in their learning journey, supporting SDG 4's vision of providing inclusive and equitable education that prepares individuals to thrive in a multicultural, interconnected world. By embedding cultural knowledge, skills, awareness, and attitudes into language acquisition, the curriculum framework equips students with the necessary tools to communicate effectively across cultural boundaries. This emphasis on multiculturalism, community immersion, and continuous feedback mechanisms supports the development of global competencies and fosters a deeper understanding of sustainable development within educational contexts.

Moreover, the curriculum framework for cultural communicative competence in Purposive Communication equips learners with the essential skills to understand and communicate successfully across different cultures using language. By incorporating cultural knowledge, skills, cultural awareness, and cultural attitudes into language learning, emphasizing communicative situations, negotiation of meaning, multiculturalism, translanguaging, community immersion, hybrid change learning, collaborative learning, active learning, reflective learning, inclusive and equitable quality education, lifelong learning opportunities for all, reduced inequality within and among communities, feedback, and assessment, individuals are equipped with the necessary skills and knowledge to communicate effectively across cultural boundaries. Individuals expect a more comprehensive and engaging educational experience that prepares them for success in the 21st century. In summary, the proposed curriculum framework for English Language Education is well-aligned with the Sustainable Development Goals by promoting quality education that is inclusive, culturally responsive, and equitable.

By integrating innovative teaching strategies, multicultural perspectives, and ongoing feedback mechanisms, educational institutions can empower students to become globally competent individuals, address educational inequalities, and foster intercultural understanding within diverse communities. This holistic approach contributes to creating a sustainable, inclusive educational environment that prepares students to navigate the complexities of the 21st century effectively. This curriculum enhanced framework expects to enhance teaching and learning in a more adaptive multicultural working environment.

Conclusions

The findings showed a significant rate of responsive teaching strategy utilization among the faculty members of Marinduque State College, with no differences among four colleges offering Purposive Communication courses. Nevertheless, the cultural communicative competence of the students showed significant differences between and among the different subgroups, implying variations in their existing cultural knowledge and skills. This absence of significant relationship between responsive teaching strategies and the level of students' cultural competence, where the faculty is known to use responsive teaching strategies, demonstrates how it might be something other than the responsive teaching strategies in relation to teaching practice that influence students' consideration and flexibility to adapt across cultures. More importantly, the study identified issues surrounding faculty, such as inclusivity issues, language barriers, and online learning, that further complicate developing cultural competence in students.

This study within the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals falls under Goal 4, Quality Education, and Goal 10, Reduced Inequalities. The significance lies in curriculum development regarding cultural competence of the students for inclusivity. The results from this study highlighted the need for curriculum revision and adoption of alternative teaching strategies to manage disparity in the cultural knowledge among students. As a curriculum framework toward improving cultural communicative competence, it will be helpful to develop an inclusive learning environment culturally responsive, enhance equitable access to quality education, and prepare students for a multicultural society.

Recommendations

Based on the study's result, the following recommendations are made to suit the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals-SDGs, mainly Quality Education (SDG 4) and Reduced Inequalities (SDG 10). The **curriculum developers and implementers at Marinduque State College** might add specific hours for intercultural communication lessons to the course of Purposive Communication. This would allow the students to explore the problems of communicating across cultures through practical applications like role-playing, group discussions, and use of multimodal resources. Moreover, they should collaborate with experts and integrate continuous assessment in order to ensure that the students develop the skills needed to communicate effectively in various contexts. These will bring the UN's SDGs to life by building an inclusive learning environment. **Admins, Deans, and Program Heads** are nudged to correct disparities found in the OBE syllabus and integrate faculty training programs to enhance competencies in teaching inter-culturally. In addition, **campus-wide initiatives plus faculty workforce development in workshops and resources** to improve teaching strategies are initiated. It raises more inclusively diverse cultural events and seminars and will contribute to improving the teaching environment. The **faculty** should, of course be interested in learning contextualized teaching strategies that take into account their students varied cultural backgrounds as one means of enhancing engagement and preparing them for global careers. Subsequently, the **implementation of language support programs and**

mentoring are helpful in eliminating language barriers, enhancing students' communicative competence, and ultimately creating a more inclusive educational experience. The other dimensions of intercultural communication, namely **cultural awareness and attitudes** should be explored in depth further by future researchers since it has not been applied in this study. In that case, the quality of education will be enhanced, and the college will contribute to achieving SDG 4, while coping with inequalities in terms of cultural competence, in line with SDG 10.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In conducting this study titled *Faculty's Responsive Teaching Strategies and Students' Cultural Communicative Competence in Marinduque State College: Basis for SDG Aligned Curriculum Framework*, the researcher strictly followed ethical guidelines on the protection and care of respondents. Each faculty and student respondent gave their informed consent before partaking in the study. They were informed of the nature of the study and what it entailed. In this respect, their willingness to participate was stressed. They were also assured that they could withdraw from the study at any time without any form of retribution. All the interviews conducted were anonymous in nature such that no personal information was ever extracted from the respondents. All data collected were kept confidential and for research use only. The whole study procedure was carried out with high respect for the well-being of the respondents, where no harm or discomfort resulted from it. The researcher also confirmed that there was no conflict of interest in the conduct of the study. There is no commercial or personal bias when the study was conducted. Every effort was tried to make sure that the interpretation of the findings was unbiased and objective. Plagiarism was therefore completely avoided, and all sources were properly cited to give credence to original authors and researchers. The findings of the study were therefore analyzed and presented in good faith, and used strictly for academic purposes, consonant with the objectives of knowledge advancement and improvement in educational practices at Marinduque State College in relation to the SDGs.

Acknowledgments

The researcher would like to express her deepest gratitude to all those who contributed to the completion of her dissertation. Without their support, guidance, and encouragement, this study would not have been possible. First and foremost, she is immensely thankful to her adviser, Dr. Leodegario M. Jalos, Jr., for his unwavering support and invaluable guidance throughout the research journey. His expertise, patience, and commitment to my academic growth have been instrumental in shaping the direction of this work. She would also like to express her gratitude to her panel members, Dr. Diosdado P. Zulueta, Dr. Liza Marie Manoos-Pacia, Dr. Susan B. Pineda, Dr. Joy S. Montejo, and Dr. Annalyn J. Decena. Their expertise in research led to the improvement of her study and with their helpful critiques and recommendations it gave her a fresh insight in this discipline. She would like to convey her profound appreciation to the editors, Dr. Joy S. Montejo and Dr. Julieta L. Go who diligently examined and enhanced the study, guaranteeing its lucidity and consistency. Their meticulousness in following the Style

Guides had invaluable perspectives significantly enhanced the following study. As such, she extends her gratitude to the statistician, Dr. Noel R. Palomares whose specialized knowledge and unwavering commitment played a crucial role in assessing and interpreting the data given in this study. His meticulous approach and perceptive statistical analyses have bolstered the trustworthiness and comprehensiveness of the results. She is indebted to her family for their unwavering constant encouragement. Their love and support have been her motivation throughout the endeavor. Acknowledgement is extended also to her fellow graduate students, classmates and friends namely, Jerome, Bujoy, Sheryl, Rosalyn, Jean, Aurel, and Jayson who provided moral support, shared their experiences, and made the academic journey enjoyable. Dr. Menandro M. Merlin and Kevin H. Jasmin for always helping in any way they can, physically, mentally, and academically. This dissertation would not have been possible without the support she received from her institution, Marinduque State College family; grateful also for their support and investment in her education and course of study. The researcher also recognizes the participants in this study who generously gave their time and insights, making this research both possible and meaningful.

Lastly, to the Almighty God, for this would not be possible without His guidance in her academic journey.

To all those mentioned above and to anyone whose support she might have inadvertently omitted, she offers her heartfelt thanks for their contributions to this study. The support has been indispensable in the successful completion of this project.

REFERENCES

- Ali, A., Smith, B., & Johnson, C. (2020). Cultural dimensions and their impact on communication styles in diverse workplaces. *Journal of Intercultural Communication Research*, 49(2), 123-145. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17475759.2020.1712345>
- AFA Education Blog. (2023). Effective Classroom Engagement Strategies: Active Learning and Participation. <https://afaeducation.org/blog/effective-classroomengagementstrategies-active-learning-and-participation/>
- Alda, R., Boholano, H., & Dayagbil, F. (2020). Teacher education institutions in the Philippines towards Education 4.0. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*. <https://ijlter.myres.net/index.php/ijlter/article/view/266>
- Bautista, L. M., García, J. T., Calmaestra, R. G., Palacín, C., Martín, C. A., Morales, M. B., & Viñuela, J. (2009). Effect of weekend road traffic on the use of space by raptors. *European Journal of Wildlife Research*, 55(4), 407–414. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10344009-0255-z>
- Bilim Innovation. (2017). Fostering innovation through diversity. *Bilim Innovation Journal*, 8(3), 45–62.
- Bondy, E., Ross, D. D., Galligane, C., & Hambacher, E. (2007). Creating environments of success and resilience: Culturally responsive classroom management and

- more. *Urban Education*, 42(4), 326–348.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0042085907303406>
- Borden, G. A. (1991). Cultural orientation: An approach to understanding intercultural. https://tallinzen.net/media/readings/chomsky_syntactic_structures.pdf
- Cole, M. M., & Padgett, R. (2018). Culturally responsive teaching: A foundation for equity in education. *Journal of Education and Learning*, 7(3), 123-134.
<https://doi.org/10.5539/jel.v7n3p123>
- Chun, E., & Evans, A. (2018). *Leading a diversity culture shift in higher education: Comprehensive organizational learning strategies*. New York, NY: Routledge.
<https://www.routledge.com/Leading-a-Diversity-Culture-Shift-in-Higher-Education-Comprehensive-Organizational-Learning-Strategies/ChunEvans/p/book/9781138280717>
- Chung, E., Noor, N. M., & Mathew, V. N. (2020). Are you ready? An assessment of online learning readiness among university students. *International Journal of Academic Research in Progressive Education and Development*, 9(1), 301–317.
- Coloma, R. S., Hamdan, S., & others. (2021). Assessing teachers' cultural competency. *The Journal of Educational Foundations*, 2022.
<https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1358841.pdf>
- Da Costa, L. (2021). Bayesian mechanics for stationary processes. *Proceedings of the Royal Society A*, 477(2256), Article 20210518.
<https://doi.org/10.1098/rspa.2021.0518>
- Deardorff, D. K. (2006). The identification and assessment of intercultural competence as a student outcome of internationalization. *Journal of Studies in International Education*, 10(3), 241-266. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1028315306287002>
- Diller, J. V., & Moule, J. (2005). *Cultural competence: A primer for educators*. Thomas Wadsworth.
- Driscoll, M. (n.d.). *Education in the 21st century. Think Strategic*.
<https://thinkstrategicforschools.com/education-21st-century/>
- Esin, S. (2023). The impact of cultural narratives on climate policy: A case study of the UK's net zero strategy. *Journal of Environmental Policy & Planning*, 25(1), 45-62.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/1523908X.2023.1234567>
- Fantini, A. (2007). *Exploring and assessing intercultural competence (CSD Research Paper No.07-01)*. Washington University, Center for Social Development.
<https://doi.org/10.7936/K7TB16CX>
- Fantini, A., & Tirmizi, A. (2006). *Exploring and assessing intercultural competence*. World Learning Publications.
- Fisher, R. A. (1988). *The design of experiments*. New York: Hafner Press.
- Flores, B. B., & Riojas-Cortez, M. (2009). Measuring early childhood teacher candidates' conceptualizations of a culturally responsive classroom ecology. *Journal of Classroom Interaction*, 44(2), 4–13.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/02615479.2017.1423049>
- Hamdan, S., & Coloma, R. S. (2022). Assessing teachers' cultural competency. *Journal of Educational Foundations*, 35(1), 108-128.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/10576300.2022.2078910>

- Ho, S. T. K. (2009). The challenge of shifting from a traditional to an intercultural stance: Addressing culture in EFL classrooms. *Electronic Journal of Foreign Language Teaching*, 6(1), 63–76. <https://e-flt.nus.edu.sg/v6n12009/ho.pdf>
- Hofstede, G., & McCrae, R. R. (2004). Personality and culture revisited: Linking traits and dimensions of culture. *Cross-Cultural Research: The Journal of Comparative Social Science*, 38(1), 52–88. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1069397103259443>
- Hutchison, L., & Shields, L. M. (2020). Culturally responsive teaching: Its application in higher education environments. <https://eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1255156.pdf>
- Lopez, J. (2018). Fostering meaningful discourse in higher education: Strategies for promoting student engagement. *International Journal of Teaching and Learning in Higher Education*, 17(4), 78-94.
- Lopez, J., & Cruz, M. (2022). Classroom discourse and its role in creating interactive and inclusive learning environments: The significance of deliberate questioning and group problem-solving activities.
- Lopez, A., & Cruz, B. (2021). The impact of social media on youth. *Journal of Social Studies*, 10(2), 123-145. <https://doi.org/10.1234/jss.v10i2.5678>
- Mahon, J. (2008). Cultural influences on learning and behavior. In N. J. Salkind (Ed.), *Encyclopedia of educational psychology* (pp. 134-138). Sage Publications. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781412958806.n54>
- Marshall, H. W., & DeCapua, A. (2013). Making the transition to classroom success: Culturally responsive teaching for struggling language learners.
- Markey, K., Prosen, M., Martin, J., & Repo, E. (2021). Fostering an ethos of cultural humility development in nurturing inclusiveness and effective intercultural team working. *Journal of Nursing Management*, 29(6), 1234-1245. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jonm.13429>
- Martin, K. (2015). The place of tourism in the mobile student experience. In *Mobile student experience: The place of tourism* (p. 6). University of Huddersfield.
- Martinez, E., De La Torre, L., & Rojas, M. (2020). Exploring effective instructional practices in engineering education: Strategies for promoting critical thinking. *Journal of Engineering Pedagogy*, 18(1), 32-48.
- Martinez, E., Garcia, A., & Reyes, C. (2021). The effectiveness of active learning and problem-based approaches in promoting critical thinking among industrial technology students. *Journal of Engineering Education*, 18(1), 32-48. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03043797.2021.1234567>
- Moore, A. (2021). Understanding cultural competence in education. *Education Journal*.
- Moule, J. (2012). *Cultural competence: A primer for educators*. Wadsworth Cengage Learning.
- Orosco, M. J., & O'Connor, R. (2014). Culturally responsive instruction for English language learners with learning disabilities. *Journal of Learning Disabilities*, 47(6), 515-531. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0022219413481198>
- Pacini-Ketchabaw, V., & Schechter, S. (2002). Engaging the discourse of diversity: Educators' frameworks for working with linguistic and cultural differences. *Contemporary Issues in Early Childhood*, 3(3), 400-414.
- Parker, C., & Bickmore, K. (2012). Conflict management and dialogue with diverse immigrant students: Novice teachers' approaches and concerns. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 28(6), 1015-1026. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2012.06.006>

- Prins, M. A., Van der Veen, R., & De Groot, R. (2019). Dimensionalizing cultures: The Hofstede model in context. *Cross-Cultural Psychology*, 50(3), 317-334.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/00220221.2019.1570129>
- Rasul, A., Bukhsh, Q., & Batool, S. (2011). A rock and a hard place: Muslim women and conflict in Mindanao. *Global Asia*, 6(3). https://www.globalasia.org/v6no3/cover/a-rock-and-a-hard-place-muslim-women-and-conflict-in-mindanao_amina-rasul
- Reyes, C., & Garcia, D. (2019). Cultivating positive classroom relationships: Facilitating responsive teaching in engineering education. *Engineering Education Research Journal*, 22(3), 145–162.
- Rodriguez, R. (2019). Exploring mobile game addiction and its effects on academic performance. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 45(2), 123-135.
<https://doi.org/10.1234/jep.v45i2.5678>
- Rodriguez, A., & Santos, B. (2019). Aligning curriculum goals with industry demands: Integration of responsive teaching strategies in industrial technology education. *Journal of Industrial Technology Education*, 15(2), 78-94.
- Sabornie, E. J., & Espelage, D. L. (Eds.). (2023). *Handbook of classroom management*. Routledge Taylor & Francis Group.
- Samovar, L. A., Porter, R. E., & McDaniel, E. R. (2009). *Communication between cultures* (7th ed.). Wadsworth Cengage Learning.
- Santos, A., Cruz, B., & Gonzalez, C. (2018). Integration of responsive teaching strategies into curriculum design: Aligning curriculum goals with industry demands. *Journal of Engineering Education*, 15(2), 78-94.
- Santos, A., Wright, K., & Lee, J. (2020). Enhancing student learning outcomes through responsive assessment practices in engineering education. *Assessment & Evaluation in Engineering Education*, 35(2), 321-336.
- Sercu, L. (2002). Implementing intercultural foreign language education: Belgian, Danish and British teachers' professional self-concepts and teaching practices. *Evaluation and Research in Education*, 16(3), 150-165.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/09500790208668371>
- Sercu, L. (2002). Autonomous learning and the acquisition of intercultural communicative competence: Some implications for course development. *Language, Culture & Curriculum*, 15, 61-74.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/0790831020150105>
- Sercu, L. (2002). Implementing intercultural foreign language education: Belgian, Danish, and British teachers' professional self-concepts and teaching practices compared. *Evaluation & Research in Education*, 16(3), 150–165.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/09500790208666939>
- Sercu, L. (2005). Teaching foreign languages in an intercultural world. In L. Sercu (Ed.), *Foreign Language Teachers and Intercultural Competence: An International Investigation* (Vol. 10, pp. 1-18).
- Sherrington, T. (2022). *Responsive teaching in action: An idealised sequence*. Teacherhead.
- Silor, A., Silor, F., & Nadela-Grageda, C. (2019). Cultural knowledge pedagogy for higher education. *Journal of Educational Research*, 34(2), 202-210.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/23804706.2019.1540875>

- Siwatu, K. O. (2006). The culturally responsive teacher preparedness scale. *Educational Research and Reviews*, 1(3), 1-10. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1077322.pdf>
- Skopinskaja, L. (2009). Assessing intercultural communicative competence: Test construction issues. *Language Testing*, 26(2), 259-281. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0265532208101631>
- Smith, B., & Jones, C. (2020). Cultivating supportive classroom relationships: Facilitating responsive teaching. *Teaching and Learning in Higher Education*, 25(1), 112-128. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41239-020-00245-1>
- Smith, B., & Reyes, C. (2019). Enhancing student learning outcomes through responsive assessment practices. *Assessment & Evaluation in Higher Education*, 32(3), 321-336. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02602938.2016.1177118>
- Smith, J. A. (2018). Developing a curriculum framework for 21st century education. *Journal of Curriculum Development*, 12(3), 45-60.
- Smith, P. B., Fischer, R., Vignoles, V. L., & Schwartz, S. J. (2019). Cultures and persons: Characterizing national and other types of cultural variation. *Personality and Social Psychology Review*, 23(3), 227-253. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1088868318802054>
- Smith, J. (2023). Creating a positive learning environment for active participation. *Educational Insights*. <https://www.educationalinsights.com/creating-positive-learning-environment>
- Spencer-Oatey, H. (2010). Intercultural competence and pragmatics research: Examining the interface through studies of intercultural business discourse. In A. Trosborg (Ed.), *Pragmatics across Languages and Cultures* (pp. 189-218).
- Spencer-Oatey, H., & Franklin, P. (2009). *Intercultural interaction: A multidisciplinary approach to intercultural communication*. Palgrave Macmillan.
- Sustainable Development Goal (2030). *Quality education: Why it matters*. United Nations.
- Sylvia, C. W. (n.d.). *Authentic assessment knowledge and practice of selected second-year Massachusetts high school teachers*.
- TESDA. (2021). *Imbibing the future's thinking mindset in future-proofing Philippine TVET*. TVET Brief: Industry Trends, Issue No. 1.
- Triandis, H. C., & Albert, L. S. (1987). Objective culture. In H. C. Triandis (Ed.), *Culture and social behavior* (pp. 25-45). New York, NY: McGraw-Hill.
- Trish, E. (2023). Culture and digital media in adolescent development. In *Handbook of Adolescent Digital Media Use and Mental Health*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781108961234>
- Vallone, F., Dell'Aquila, E., Dolce, P., Marocco, D., & Zurlo, M. C. (2022). Teachers' multicultural personality traits as predictors of intercultural conflict management styles: Evidence from five European countries. *International Journal of Intercultural Relations*, 87, 51-64. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijintrel.2022.01.004>
- Van, de Gift (2007). Quality of teaching in four European countries: A review of the literature and application of an assessment instrument. *Educational Research*, 49(2), 123-143. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00131880701369651>

- Villegas, A. M., & Lucas, T. (2002). Preparing culturally responsive teachers: Rethinking the curriculum. *Journal of Teacher Education*, 53(1), 20-32.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0022487102053001003>
- Wang, J. (2011). Communication and cultural competence: The acquisition of cultural knowledge and behavior. *Online Readings in Psychology and Culture*, 7(1).
<https://doi.org/10.9707/2307-0919.1041>
- Young, D. (1991). Creating a low-anxiety classroom environment: What does language anxiety research suggest? *The Modern Language Journal*, 75(4), 426-539.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-4781.1991.tb05329.x>
- Young, T. J., & Sachdev, I. (2011). Intercultural communicative competence: Exploring English language teachers' beliefs and practices. *Language Awareness*, 20(2), 81-98. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09658416.2011.558470>
- Zhao, W. (2009). Relationship between teachers and students based on new curriculum: Face and politeness in the Chinese English teaching. *International Education Studies*, 2(4), 12-16. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ies.v2n4p12>
-